

Day 1 TOPS October 2022 - Part 1

Tue, Oct 25, 2022 12:33PM • 3:55:16

SUMMARY KEYWORDS

science, nasa, open, community, tops, data, conferences, question, people, share, research, discussion, develop, build, talk, event, slides, meeting, thinking, lead

SPEAKERS

Cynthia Hall, chelle gentemann, Brianna Pagan, Qiusheng Wu, Logan Kilpatrick, Jim Colliander, Laura Lyon, Malvika Sharan, Monica Granados, Fernando Perez, isabella martinez, ch, Marshall Styczinski, Yvonne Ivey, Kevin Murphy, Jordan Adams, brooks hanson, Brian Nosek, SherAaron Hurt, Pen-Yuan Hsing, Kristina Vrouwenvelder

BEGINNING OF TRANSCRIPT - Note this transcript may contain errors, please view the recording to confirm speakers and text.

chelle gentemann 00:28

hi, everyone. I'm Chelle Gentemann. And I was Isley for jobs. And next slide, please. So, this is similar to the spring meeting, where we had you all virtual, but now we actually have to do this in person. So the goal here is to act as a review panel for our project, and provide constructive feedback on our missions, our plans, our recent activities, and the panelists will serve as a representative of their community, speak to their experiences with open science, provide lessons learned and conducting open science and provide input on future steps to be taken by tops top partners, and the greater NASA scientific community. At the end is is we use the transcript and work with you like we did in this range, provide a written report. And all of this is going to be published, it will be recorded, a transcript will be made public and then the written report will end up using problems. Our goal here is to really recognize that you are the ones who have been doing the work in the open science community over the last decade or two. And NASA is coming in as a supporter of open science. So we don't want to come in and be a disruptive supporter, we want to come in and be a constructive influence. And that's really why we're having this panel is we want to know, we want your honest opinions about what you think we're doing that's working, what's not working, what should we thinking about what are we missing, and really try to help us be part of the Open Science movement that you all can bring. And so we really appreciate your honest opinions and your voice. And we encourage you to give us very straight, constructive feedback and become. Thank you. Next slide. here's our agenda, essentially review introductions icebreaker. Then we're going to go right into the thoughts updates, and spring panel feedback and actions that we've taken to address some of your comments and questions that we still have about some of them. And then to talk about the year of open science activities and partnerships and

discussion about any gaps that we may have. Cindy the code of conduct, we expect all persons to be treated with respect and consideration. Be considerate, respectful and collaborative, communicate openly with respect for others avoid personal attacks, be mindful of your virtual surroundings and alert a host if you notice a dangerous situation. Please respect the rules and policy of the virtual meeting space and unacceptable behaviors harassment, intimidation, physical or verbal abuse. There's some examples given the disruptive. And next slide please. And anyone requested Assad was expected to comply immediately. And we may take actions that we deem necessary and appropriate to maintain a safe space. Please, if you're subject or you see anything, you see something, say something, contact myself via chat via slack via email, or just pulled me aside and let me know that something's going on that you're uncomfortable with.

Cynthia Hall 04:23

Show maybe if you can come closer to my computer. Okay, that's what the sounds go

chelle gentemann 04:27

through. Thank you. Okay, next. So we have a QR code that we're going to use to collect questions and feedback. And this is a lot mostly for the online people. So we can put that QR code in the chat for the WebEx people, please. And that's where it's an im tool. You can submit questions and if we have time as we have time, during discussions, we'll try to get to some of this. But mostly here we're going to focus on the panel feedback. Next slide.

Yvonne Ivey 04:57

I'm not sure if the microphones actually working. So I will stand up for here. And I would just say apologize for the folks on the call. We're trying to figure out how to get sounds work. Next slides any. All right. So, um, big thank you to all of our community panelists who have been supporting talks over the past year, we have some folks in the room. And so I would just like to welcome everyone again, and also the folks on the call. We've gotten so, so much great feedback, not only from the original document that you put together from our panel today, but also folks reaching out and asking how do they apply next year to get involved with us. And so thank you so much for helping us pioneer this activity at NASA. Next slide. We're gonna jump into the fun part right now. Alright, so we're gonna have an icebreaker. I'll have Cindy, walk everyone through kind of the expectations and what we're going to

Cynthia Hall 06:09

do. Thank you very much. So hi, good morning, everyone. I'm Cynthia Hall, the Community Coordinator for the Tots program. Excited to be here with all of you. So we need to get to know you all better. We have some postcards and in person. We have postcards here that I'm gonna share. And we also have a jam board for our virtual panelists, that you can also go on and pick a postcard what we want you to do is we have a bunch of NASA images pick the postcard that most resonates with you as far as what your ethos of open science. Yeah, you can everybody can pick the one that they want that most resonates with them. And then we're going to have you quickly tell us why that resonates with you why you chose to energy and why that resonates with you. And virtual panelist if you'll please join a jam board and put your name on the image FSH you want to make sure we are completely inclusive source. So we'll just in a few minutes. I want to come up here So now we're going to login. So now if you have your credit card, we'll have everyone come up. And unfortunately, you'll have to come up here

to my computer, because that's the speaker that the virtual participants are listening from. And tell us, why do you try to show us the image that you've picked? Why you pick that image, and how that resonates with you regarding open Smith's. So we'll start with the in person, a couple of in person, then we'll go online and get some of our virtual panelists. So does anyone want to start us off? Anyone willing to go first? Yeah, go around.

chelle gentemann 12:47

So I did see evidence, LiDAR, and deep in the ocean cinematographer. And I like to explore unknown faces, they find that I think I have an unnatural fear of risk. So light.

Kevin Murphy 13:08

Got it? Sure. So I take a picture of the ocean. And I just thought this, this is a left. I think that, you know, this is kind of one of the reasons why we're here right is to understand how these natural processes work. And especially with better receding ice, that we need a lot of people

Marshall Styczinski 13:45

I chose an image of Jupiter also, which by the name of a Marshall stuczynski M at JPL, and it was socked. And I chose the image of Jupiter because I've always loved Jupiter since I was a kid. And a lot of the science that I'm doing is relating to Jupiter and that's just always made my code open for for helping other people get access to the same tools. So it resonated with me because of that.

brooks hanson 14:12

So rexine 72 Lena Delta shakes off winter. That was a pretty good metaphor for where we are. And it's also kind of fractal and I thought that was a good metaphor to hold on

Laura Lyon 14:27

to you, minus pose for now that space person so I can't really describe it well, but the reason I chose it is because I feel like it really kind of is quintessential NASA there's like very inspirational telescope shots. And like that, because I feel like that's a lot of people sort of initial inspiration to get into science kind of sparks that wonder and I think that's really represented.

Kristina Vrouwenvelder 14:53

And Christina and I chose this one which is a couple of years of faraway Galaxy through a cosmic lens and I'm a chemist by training and the most common reaction I get on airplanes to people ask me in my profession is, oh, I hated chemistry. And I don't think people have that reaction to astronomers usually, or at least I hope not. I think that's the thing that's really cool about having these kinds of images be part of your science. And I think that it's an opportunity for open science. I want it to serve as a way to connect with the broader community, not just between scientists, but between the public and scientists. And that's why it has this postcard

Cynthia Hall 15:31

logon. Would you mind coming up here to the computer or everyone else? If you'll come up here? That'd be great.

15:36

We want to do something.

Cynthia Hall 15:39

Yeah, why don't we switch to? Hugh Shang? Do you want to go ahead and show tell us your picture and why you chose that?

Qiusheng Wu 15:52

Yeah, I choose images. Number four, I believe is probably a Landsat image. And so this kind of the NSA imagery that I've been using for machine monitoring years now, and I'm very grateful that NASA and us make a freely available to anyone around the globe, and a lot of our cloud computing, why now be on top load data from the public domain, especially from NASA in us, Andy has Empower so many applications, and also, it makes resource more reproducible and more accessible. So I benefit a lot personally, from lot of the satellite data from NASA. So it resonates with me a lot with least imaging.

Cynthia Hall 16:41

Thank you for sharing parently you, have you chosen an image?

Pen-Yuan Hsing 16:50

Okay. Yes, I did choose one. Thank you. My name is Alicia, you can just call me pen. I'm really sorry, I can't be there with you in person today. But I'm honored to be here virtual. So I picked postcard number five on the so called the jam board along with Brian. It is the image of the sun rising from behind the earth. And you can see every thin, you know, reflection of the Earth's atmosphere in this picture. And it reminds me of the same picture being shown many years ago when I saw the film and inconvenient truth about climate change. It really inspired me because it makes me think about the fragility of the Earth that we share together, and the importance of open science to rapidly innovate as we work together to solve the challenges of today. So that's my pick. Thank you.

Cynthia Hall 17:52

Brian, I see you chose the same image. So you want to tell us why you chose that image as well.

Brian Nosek 17:58

Sure, I wish I had as compelling a reason as Penn did that was more inspirational than mine, which was evoked for me a sense of the dawn of the age of open science. So here we go.

Cynthia Hall 18:11

That's great. Thank you. I think we'll come back to our in person, Brett or John Logan. Yeah, thanks.

Logan Kilpatrick 18:25

Awesome. How's it going everyone, my name is Lauren Glasser, board of directors. And I'm focused and also the developer advocate for the children programming language. I chose the image of the Mars perseverance launch in July 2017. Just because I think open sciences is sort of the rocket fuel, if you will, of a lot of innovation that's happening. Awesome. And also sort of a combination of a ton of hard

work from a lot of people like what it takes to make a rocket launch happen. So excited to be here. And I'll hand it off to Jim. Thanks.

brooks hanson 19:02

Hello, everyone, I'm Jim Oleander from UBC and 2i2c. And I chose image number, which is an image of a solar flare. And I chose to quickly because I was inspired by a meeting that I participated in in June, celebrating the life of Jack Eddie Eddie symposium. And through that meeting, I observed that heliophysics connects all these different branches of science in interesting ways to try to help us understand living in an environment around the sun, and synthetic way of putting together all of science inspired me. And the other fact about this that really made me want to choose this image is the long 22 year cycle of the sun makes me think about the long process that we're undergoing and trying to transform science and I think we should think on decades scale rather than quarter scale or a year long scale.

Cynthia Hall 19:55

Great. Thank you, Sharon. Good day, everyone.

SherAaron Hurt 19:58

I am Sure, Aaron, I'm with the carpet trees. And I can image number seven. NASA's interstellar boundary explorers spacecraft maps the boundaries of the heliosphere. So for me, I didn't even pay attention to what the backside and I picked it for the front, which was the color. It drew me. And instantly, it made me think optimism. But it also showed to me a global world, which is what we're trying to do, you know, the year of 2023. But when we look at all the individual colors, they're small, there's people are impacted, you have a large impact. But then you have those champions, the smaller colors that are, you know, you have a small impact and a big impact. But ultimately, it's impacting the globe, and it's a little fuzzy, but as we continue to work to begin to get

Monica Granados 20:47

clear. Great, thank you. Buddy, I am Monica Granados, I am the opening climate campaign manager at Creative Commons. And I'm going to leadership team of three review. I chose postcard number 15. It's the Space Launch System core stage being lowered inside high bay, three of the vehicle, Assembly Building attendee. And the reason that we chose this is because it is awe inspiring the kind of image where you look in off, but it's incredible that humans can do this. And this is similar. But you know, we said earlier, it's a culmination of years of science and innovation, that science is a process, you know, that works on, you know, the shoulders of people who come before you. And the only way that we will continue to make innovations like this is that the knowledge about how, you know, the rocket fuel worked, and the idea of propulsion, and you know, those fundamental basics were available, and Sophie continue to make science available, we can continue to innovate.

Malvika Sharan 22:02

Great, thank you. Hi, hi, everyone. I'm representing the children way, and open life science. I chose also number 20, which is the total solar Atlas, July 2019, a composite device. The reason I waited is because it just reminded me of the view from my home in London. And the reason I like it is that all my life I lived in Nordrhein. I never had a view of helping from this island. But then taking off the art and

science, I'm also very much thinking in that same sense is that suddenly I have this view that I can share with people and that is very bad. So yeah, not very profound.

Brianna Pagan 22:53

That's great. Hi, my name is Brianna Pradhan, I am the engineering lead at one of the docks at NASA based out of here in LA. I chose postcard number 12, which was researchers successfully bio mine and EDM aboard the space station. And is the closest thing to remind me of my own PhD research was was looking at plant vegetation health from space. But it just reminded me how I never want to myself conduct science or allow other sciences to work in that way where research on my private computer, I have all my codes stored in some external drives that are sitting in my house for no one ever to see again. And I'm happy to be part of a team that's now helping scientists, or at least enable science, and excited to talk about

isabella martinez 23:41

that. Thank you. Hello, everyone. My name is Val Martinez is a member of the top 14. But you didn't meet me last time because unfortunately, I wasn't able to make the last panel Hello, nice to meet you. My pronouns are she her? I checked postcard number 14. And I chose last because I didn't realize it was participating in the icebreaker. So that gave me a little nudge. And I think I probably would have chosen this one anyway, because I thought out of what the earth and the moon look like from the other side of Saturn's rings. And I did when I look at this beyond just thinking that it was beautiful. And I think it's a good story about different kinds of science being used to do something incredible take a photo of the earth are so far away. I think it represents the way that we are trying to take a step back almost in this project from the minutiae and the details of individual sciences or fields or individual missions and seeing all of us should be for all and I think that

Laura Lyon 24:54

is pretty incredible. Hey y'all.

Yvonne Ivey 25:06

I'm Yvonne Ivey, I'm the equity lead for Tots. And so I chose postpartum recovery, which are moving Glantz beans off lakes in the US Canadian border. i To be honest, I picked it up simply because I love the image. But I think I'm gonna tie this to like open science and how having access and to understand the moon is one of the really cool niches in Athens exploring right now. And I think that when I look at those, and I think about kind of my journey and to like, falling in love with HR and better understanding kind of the role that I play in the broader sort of global ecosystem, I think about the time that I went to Canada, and I spent so much time in Montreal, and I just fell in love with nature and geography and just being in the outdoors. And I think that that's whatever really holdings that we're exploring when it comes to broadening participation and getting more involved with bringing folks who are most impacted by the numerous crises that are happening on a global scale when I think about how science can truly help inform decision making, but also being able to provide access to data to the folks who need it the most. It's one of the aspects that I think this work will allow for.

Cynthia Hall 26:41

Simply trying to troubleshoot how to make it easier for you all to hear and hear for our online guests. So we'll continue to troubleshoot that as we move through the meeting. But hopefully we'll get this worked out by the first break. I think I'm the last one to go. Did we get all our panelists online? Great. I chose postcard number 18, which are cyclones of color and Jupiter's North Pole. And cyclones at the North Pole Jupiter appears swirls of striking colors on and this is for NASA's Juno mission. And I think one of the most exciting things for me when I joined the Topps team I was hearing chelle and Yvonne talk about inclusion and diversity and equity. And that really resonated with me, as a female geologist. Going to school I didn't have there were, there's really no one color in my department that I went to. And this is one of a handful of females. And so broadening participation by those that have been historically marginalized and so on, and it's really something I'm passionate about, and I think opens my eyes towards that. And I just loved all that color and hear it reminds me of diversity and how everything's kind of meshing together. And I think that's what open science is gonna help us do. So thank you I hope you'll enjoy that you can take your postcard if you want to. And thank you for doing that for us. It was really interesting to hear your thoughts if we want to change

29:36

Alright, so myself limit Kumar, I work with the Indian National Center for Ocean Information Services. And that was the reason for the postcard that I picked and I also happen to be associated with the some of the groups internationally, such like pan ocean remote sensing conference, as well as the group Have group on the Earth observations. So I am part of the one of the tour groups, that is Terms of Reference for the Earth observation data for the fisheries. So basically, I'm the operational oceanographer who makes use of the satellite remote sensing data for these social applications. And the r&d that I have been involved with, that actually caters to many hundreds of 1000s, not to exaggerate that hundreds of 1000s of the just one user community, I'm talking about fisherman within India on the daily basis. So I'm here for the first time, I have gone through the slides that were made available to us. Due to time difference, it might be very difficult for me to stay with you full day. So maybe sessions after lunchtime, I might be around the main curiosity or interest for me to join these virtually, was that how you know, I mean, on the day to day scale, what we do the capacity development in the Indian Ocean region, and beyond. So, a couple of weeks back, I was in Morocco training, Moroccan researchers to how to make use of this EO data for the fisheries and aquaculture. So these kind of the activities that I take up under these groups that I mentioned about how best you know, we can actually make use of the tops program and where we can synergize that is my motivation to join today. Thanks for

Kevin Murphy 31:50

the time. Okay, thumbs up, if you can hear me online. Okay, good. There we go. So, we'll continue to work on these technical issues, as we always do with hybrid meetings. My name is Kevin Murphy, I don't think you can see me online. But that's kind of an older picture of me of like, I still look somewhat like that. I'm the Chief Science Officer with the Science Mission Directorate. I wear two hats, though. So I also work as the program manager for the Earth Science Data Systems, which is what I've been doing for many years now. And so, so we kind of made this position. We I didn't make it, I applied to it. But a lot of stand out of a series of things that we've done over the past couple years. Over the past couple years to develop a strategy for a data management computing science, for you're going to take this offline. Now this works, got. Yeah, I'm still learning how to do this after like, 20 years, it's okay. So we

made this position that I currently have SP made this position, because they really do value, how we're making these large public investments, and research data, and missions and communities that promises that information, analyze that information and use that information out to the widest group of people, right. So for a long time, NASA has had the charter to share its information publicly since the late 50s, when when the initial NASA documents are signed. Anyhow, fast forward to 2019. We've had to formalize that SMD specifically, or the Science Mission Directorate, is supporting evidence. And we recognize that just saying, Hey, we're going to support it isn't enough, right? We've got to actually commit to doing some specific things, to enable it, and to change the community's opinion about it. So I really do appreciate everybody's participation in this meeting. NASA isn't the first one to do this. shows that we are contributing to a global movement of insights. I'm, hopefully we can do some concrete things within the strategy that we've developed with your guidance. As we move forward, there are three main goals that we're going to blend capabilities to enable both good science things like policies that we have internal, continuous evolution in our data and computing systems, because we are more and more reliant on them to do the big scientific enterprises and to address the gigantic scientific problems we have. And then artists community and strategic partnerships, center foundation. This took a while to develop, we did a whole bunch of things to do it. Right, as any strategy that has, we've talked to a lot of people, both internally and externally, we sent out all the typical government things like our eyes, and this and that, and this position, that stuff that we're supposed to do. But at the end of the day, we had all of the sites division said that's headquarters, their leadership and the leadership of the Science Mission Directorate, approve this time, right. So that represents at least currently about an \$8 billion a year investment in the development of science capabilities for NASA. And those are the leadership team. So they are behind this. So you're playing an incredibly important role in helping to shape what we do here. Now, now specifically related to the programs that fall within, like my realm of responsibility, we have the same condition. So if you look through congressional justification, because that's what everybody does. And once they look at, you know, what, what imposes this section, right? Within our science, you'll see there's an Earth Science Data System Program. And within that program, there's an Open Source Initiative. And the four things that it does, right, and this is right now, I think, around a \$20 million dollar per year program is that the developer policy, we're defining and developing things Helleborus purposes, we support the community through competitive programs like roses, roses, is kind of asked to speak for grants. So if you want to apply for NASA grant, we have specific ones related to open science. And then what we're all here to talk about is tops are transformed open science, and how do we get the community to do that work? Thankfully, Michelle, and Yvonne and you know, Cindy, and Isabel and other folks in the room, and online, and so some of the core values that we have within this are that, you know, we want to be as open as possible. And as restricted as necessary, how we secure. We do a lot of work with, you know, software, with computing, with advanced algorithms with advanced designs for satellites, so on and so forth, right? We need to be as open as we possibly can be to support the science activities. But some of those things for a variety of reasons, we can't make up. Okay, we in our group, really try to keep it as open as possible. But we can get some pushback. So just to see your knowledge, we can't have everything totally open. But that's our desire. We want to increase the accessibility, inclusion and reproducibility of SMD science activities, right, as you look at at trying to recreate model output, as you try to look at things that take large amounts of data and complex software to generate, it's hard to get right, I would guarantee you or maybe not guarantee, I would challenge you to find a paper where you could do that. Within let's say we write a paper in your favorite journal and try to recreate those results. If they use, let's say NASA science data

from satellites, there's going to try to do it. I didn't find that way. I would love to hear about it. But we also realize that we're adding new things to the community. Right? So how the community has to be a primary consideration, because we don't want to stop what we're doing. Right? So in instances where we want to open up which can take more work, more documentation, new learning of how to do this work, new requirements for submitting your journals to databases or metadata or whatever it is, right? We need to look at how we can reduce that burden while still making things more accessible because we have the standards. So what about this is May 1, we have thing is, is that we got a budget back at the end, but April May timeframe. So we can actually execute something. So that was the first one. But we had nothing to do with that was just some responded Oh my god. So as we go through today's meeting, right, the first thing that we'd like to say is that this is kind of a working meeting. So, you know, we're still experimenting with how to make Open Meetings work. And we see that with our audio visual connection at this point for our remote participants. So while you make everything open at all, sometimes it's not as successful as we want to do. So we're going to hack into discussions, we're going to try to bring in both external participants or the people that are remote participants not really external. And, yeah, we're looking for ways to improve that all the time. I think if we did a poll right now, it'd be like, Hey, make sure you can hear. But yeah, well, we'll get better at that over the next next year or so. And we're trying to keep these open, because we want everybody to be involved in the process. And we want them to feel included helping us define this. Right. One of the things one of the criticisms that we've had previously is that, you know, flow sites need meetings are closed advisory meetings, really don't represent all of the people's views that range, and probably, you know, artists, so don't be self serving. So a couple things that we've specifically done. Last year, we released SPD 41, which is something it's policy director 41. And that's basically, that was basically a combination of all the existing rules, laws, regulations, and documented things that we were supposed to do with federal refund. It's next. But of all, one, stop first time as MD has ever had a policy about this need to be like, Oh, that sounds pretty easy. Well, it's not. Because you got to get all the same people that approved the initial document over this again. The second thing we did is we said, Okay, now we have a baseline for this, what are the changes that we need to make, to make things actually more than to make that strategy that I put up on the first slides, right, and that's what ste 41 A is, we basically have approval for that. But we're currently working on the implementation plan, because it's going to have a lot of changes to that committee, and we don't want to turn it on, like a light switches, blogger, they have, what we want to do is kind of like, a little bit, you know, grease Frisia things that are applying so that we have fun to adjust in the community. And we had fine and currently to develop the capabilities to resort. Right, so it's kind of twofold. Um, here are the big things that we have to manage to do. Right? Scientific data should be fair, and open to the public with clear, open accessible data licenses, right, this is what we're doing across all of SMB, be saleable, because we recognize that, you know, data is a very important component to any obligation that you do. And this includes things that we would fund as grants, right? Mission data has always been open. Or it shouldn't always, software shall be publicly available. It doesn't say that we're going to be great software, but hopefully three tops, we can make that software, make the community understand how to develop great software or better software, and be saleable, because that's also a significant contribution to help people do science with data that we create. And we're making now mission software openly available from the beginning of munitions. So if we start a new mission, so to go back to the holder, or go back and reach back like 20 years, or 10 years or five years, it starts once this policy is enabled or enacted. But everything from that point on it's due, right will be open. According to these rules, publications will no longer have a paywall. Right, that's beautiful.

And for us to and that's consistent with OCD guidance I came out after we actually paid this policy obligations will be of no force. And then the final one is how do we get all of this work done? meetings like this? in terms of supporting the community that actually provides the infrastructure for us to do science, we've made a number of great opportunities available to them, so that they can And, you know, in the funding that they need honestly, the say, occurring with with overdose, right? So software is open source software is specifically is a foundational component to our vision for open source science. We're open sets, and we're putting our money where our mouth is like. Here are some other opportunities as well, including topical workshops, symposiums conferences, right, these requests, I guess. And those of us work with people in the community, to develop workshops and conferences and things like that, to work with them. We have supplemental awards for software to open the closed software that exists out there in our communities, we have transformed open science training, which is currently open closes December 8. So if you're interested in applying that contact, or take a look online, and do that, that's going to be an incredibly important part. But I think we'll probably be talking about that a bit later. But that's going to be incredibly important. As we build off of common modules that will your AGU talk about later. So there's a really discipline specific science specific activities that really reach into your communities. And then multidomain, reusable, artificial intelligence tools, that just opens and closes January. And this is really looking at artificial intelligence and machine learning tools, especially older models, and, and how those development activities work is a lot of exoplanetary right now, but shows a lot of great interest. And we're going to continue to do that stick, right, this isn't like a one and done. This is going to be an iterative every year to a series of rows of stalls. So if you apply and you don't get something or if you know, groups that didn't know this was coming, so they didn't apply, hold them to check it off and keep on working on or at least paying attention to those announcements, because we can't talk to everybody. But that's kind of what this group is about is to get that work. The big thing is, is that, you know, finding data at NASA, or any federal government agency is very difficult, because there's typically not a central place to find it. I think that everybody has to, you know, put it all in one spot. And it's the one thing that rules everyone, but really federated catalogs of interoperable datasets, interoperable database systems allowing for Palawan reclame. Okay, all right. So we're doing that with a thing called the science discovery engine, good stuff, about 70 or 80. Remember, a million documents 80% of the data in the software catalog that we know of a moment to find sites divisions, right at the very highest level, like a you know, this piece of software exists, not the actual software, like we're going to be getting this dataset exists, but if only all the files under it, you know, so it's really just that pointer. The other thing is, is mining and making available for a deep search the contents of journals, durables is really, really important, right? And how they link up to the datasets and software. And ABS is attempting to do that. Right. So it's a very complete full text document search database for further review. We're expanding, right? So it was for astrophysics to begin with, and now it's going to be extended all five divisions. And we're going to link the science discovery engine with the astrophysics data system. So you should be able to go back and forth between the two. Okay. Now, we get to why we're really here. I don't think we're pending appropriations anymore. We have we have appropriations. So, but talks, as you probably all heard last spring, is a \$14,000,000.05 year mission to accelerate the adoption of open sights. You've probably seen these strategic goals, your job is to help us get there. Give us your thoughts on doing it. And I think that that's it and I don't think it's over but maybe there a couple minutes for questions. Last slide. So this is the SD 41 and implementation plan that is still being written before we decide exactly what we're going to do. I mean, before we publish SPD 41, and an active link sign it says active day is will have that mental mentation plan available.

Okay. And it will be disseminated to the reason it will be disseminated likely through our website. And until we get on site. Anyone online?

Cynthia Hall 51:01

There is a question from Brian. Maybe. Does he have his hand raised?

Brian Nosek 51:08

Yes. Yes, that's me. Thanks. Thanks. It's great to see the progress have been made. I had a few questions on the policy with some just some of the particulars. I'll just think they're all probably brief answers. So I'll just rattle them off. The data policy says upon publication, are there expectations in the policy about data from research that doesn't end up getting published? Does that end up getting made available? That's one. The second is wondering if the software part of the policy includes analytic code that sometimes is considered software. Other times it's just considered part of the scripting like an order and otherwise. And then the last was you mentioned, for the paper policy that aligns with the OSTP memo that came out. But I see at least on the slide, it says that there's a 12 month embargo, and the OSTP memo reduces that to zero embargo. So I wonder what the policy plan is there in terms of alignment with OSTP? So thanks.

Kevin Murphy 52:11

Yeah, so let's see, we have we are developing part of our development of the implementation plan is to clarify some of the exact questions he got. So I don't have specific answers for let's see, first of all was on date is like, you know, development and republished? You know, I think that that's in there, we've had that discussion actively, you know, the preference is to make it open. But the question is, how do you enforce it? Right, so there are a bunch of like enforcing questions on there, and how far you want to go to do that. So, you know, that was a subject or an item for discussion. The second one was like, hey, where do we draw the line with open sourcing software, or Analytics code or snippets? We do have a bit more information on that, and the FAQ that accompanies ste 41. And is being refined for SP 41. A. So I'd suggest that we take a look at that once it's finalized internally. And yeah, we've got a lot of RFI responses relative to where do you draw that line? So we're in active discussions. The last one is in terms of the period of kind of exclusivity, right, we are going to align with the OSTP memo. But we have about three years to do that, or two years, according to the OSTP memo. So you know, we want we know, we were really happy to see LSCB put that in there because that's what our original desire was. But through internal discussions, as we were actually building the policy and trying to get buy in, and approval that got pushed out. So it was very busy. We put that back in. And we're definitely gonna be following that. But it's probably going to take a year or three depending on either they had everything had to be implemented by 2025. From USDP. No. So we'll definitely have it done by then. If not, sir. Okay.

Cynthia Hall 55:52

But we'll be back in 10

brooks hanson 1:16:55

toss folks to think about those things. And that's essentially that we have an audience of students watching our conversation. And the third is kind of a feeling that I have where I have had the great

fortune and Dude, my privilege to run in r1 circles. Some people that I think about writing proposals, Swift, are the people that end up who are mostly running in our lawn service. So please find a way to connect me to enable me to interact with people that emphasize and not to do so in some sort of a, you know, on trying to save your kind of offended partner with people that I'm not connected with. So that we can together build things that actually break down disparities, right, hospitably stratifying, the certainties and one thing is all the resources and Wi Fi setup.

chelle gentemann 1:17:49

Thanks, for all your comments. Yeah, we've been thinking a lot about the deployment of open core, and actually brooks has half a day a tomorrow to assess all of those details and answer all your questions about that. But we also really want advice here about that, you know, do we carpentries, of course, a big fan. And there's a lot of questions about how we deploy this, but we're going to try to get through tomorrow. The next one, the meetings. Yes, this means we intend this to be part of it is we're just waiting office. And we intend this to be our last meeting at a NASA center. And all of our other meetings we're hoping to hold at institutions where maybe half a dozen normally go so that we can bring in new voices, new people and have more accessible, more public participation. Thank you for that prompt. And next panel, that's where we hope to be at what's the last one? The network's network. So in our October 13, call is next Thursday, and entire call is devoted to the top secret elicitation. We'll be describing it in detail. We'll be answering question and answers. Everything will be transcribed will be the FAQ. One thing that I love ideas on Twitter only. My short. This is something that we wanted to think about. Is there a way to create a Google Sheet assignment once or people who are interested or looking for partnerships, what would be a really good way to tap into how we could

Fernando Perez 1:22:07

Wait, but I'm sure that also means the problems and challenges are actually quite different. And so if you could clarify

Pen-Yuan Hsing 1:32:16

Working towards publishing, it can be hardware designs. That's something that me and the group I work with are looking into there, we're actually coming up with some standards and best practices for how to publish hardware designs for open science. They can, of course, like the open core material be educational and outreach material. I know when it comes to OER, and science education, a lot of professional scientists participate in that process, but they don't publish it either in places or in ways that enable reuse and sharing. Or, and and I think people are just starting to look into this could even be, you know, things like social media outputs from doing science, right. So it can be really diverse, and it's only limited by our imagination. So I think these are the types of things that open science publishing on outputs could could encompass. I don't know if that fully answers your question. Yeah, I

chelle gentemann 1:33:37

struggle is going to be in you guys still hear me?

Pen-Yuan Hsing 1:33:41

Kind of you got it.

chelle gentemann 1:33:45

Yeah, and I think the struggle will be sort of developing metrics, right? Because as where you we really want to encourage different types of scientific output beyond peer reviewed publications, especially given the cost of peer reviewed publications. So how do we recognize and develop metrics that that lead to funding that lead to career advancement around these other types of diverse scientific output, like notebooks? Like, you know, social media, like blogs? Does any other comments on this or we'll move to the next question that I think we have for you? Oh, yeah, so Brooks, and then Fernando.

brooks hanson 1:34:31

So I might mention this tomorrow. On educational resources, we are in collaboration about six societies are expanding preprint option for educational resources that'll be indexed and things like that, because there is a lot of kind of individual development of course, and course materials that are shared among a small group but often not shared among a large group. So you know, that's that's not a complete solution. But I think that gets out to some of the non publication value that I think we're thinking about.

Pen-Yuan Hsing 1:35:08

And yes, thank you. Um, so. So one thing I've been thinking about since, you know, everything started today is that when we talk about Open Science, right, we talk a lot about, you know, sharing things, so that in a way that they are reproducible, and they have accountability and all of that stuff. So we talk a lot about how to share and publish our outputs. But I think there is a gap right now, where less work has been done on actually doing the reproduction of science, right. There's less work on people who actually go through the process of reproducing something that has been published. But in addition to that, I think we have also seen very little from, you know, research that builds on and remixes, previous outputs that have been published as open sets. For instance, I haven't seen a lot of publications where they're like, you know, okay, we used this existing data set that was published in a way that we can use it, we didn't collect our own data. On top of that data, we analyze that in a new way, by taking existing open source code, but we tweaked it into a new thing, to enable a new set of analysis that produces a novel outcome, right? Like, I haven't seen a lot of cases where people really make use of different types of open science outputs into something new. And I was thinking about this, because, you know, one of the goals of the next several years is to produce I think it's called five major discoveries that will publish this open science. But I think we have an opportunity here where we can encourage science being done in a way that really makes use of things that have already been published as open science, if that makes sense. And this ties back to your previous point about how do we measure and encourage this kind of success. And maybe if we can develop some way of tracking, not just in terms of whether something has been published as open sites, but how much it has been not only shared and reused, but also adapted for different purposes. If we can track that as some sort of success metric that may be that can inform how we encourage people to do more open science, if that makes sense.

chelle gentemann 1:37:54

Fernando and then we'll just go around. So good,

Fernando Perez 1:38:03

kind of reflected on what Malvika said earlier about communities beyond the US a wonder if the if tops because I understand that as a NASA funded program, the ability to legally reach beyond the US is

tricky, right? But could there be ways of partnering and potentially even partnering with private philanthropy or partnering with others so that some of the funds that may be needed elsewhere come from a non NASA source if necessary, because I am reflecting on a conversation that chelle was privy to two weeks ago, but not everyone in this room was which was at CCI, the CCI open source event, there was a fantastic discussion around open science beyond North America and Western Europe. Right. And in that participation, the topic of for example, the how narrow the incentives and metrics of those communities that researchers and other countries face came up and it was very stark, right? How tightly bound to things like impact. I mean, if we think the review process in the US is bad, you should look at whether other countries us right, it really is crazy counting of things to give people salaries. And so it occurred to me that partnership and potentially as an outcome, this is just kind of I'm throwing spaghetti at the wall, that an outcome of tops could be something like a guidebook that provides an example of metrics, out types of outcomes, intellectual criteria for understanding those atoms, which is not impact factors, examples and illustrations so that he could imagine an academic and Columbia my country, going to the university Provost and saying, Look, stop counting papers here. NASA has developed these guidelines on how to do science for the next century that isn't counting impact factors and they're explaining all of these kinds of outputs and how they play a role in world class science. I know that condensing exists and carrying the imprimatur of NASA could actually help when somebody is presenting that elsewhere. It's one thing to say I'm citing this blog post from somebody on the internet versus the steam of NASA experts. And when the researchers produced this guidebook with a menu of options, I don't know.

chelle gentemann 1:40:21

I love it. It sounds like you're volunteering to help lead that with. Fernando, I think we have noticed and we'll send you. These to stand up for?

Brian Nosek 1:40:47

Thanks, it's great discussion. There's a lot of things to react to. But I'll go back to your first question of what are the other things that one might value in credit. And we usually think about open scholarship as including process outputs, and discussion evaluation. So in the outputs, Penn already described a number of those that go beyond the list that we have protocols, notebooks, etc. On process, it would be things like research, planning, pre registration, data management plans, other things that provide information about how the workflow happens. And then also, inclusion opportunities have big team science pathways for researchers to get involved with their available resources and expertise on larger projects that they wouldn't ordinarily have an opportunity to get involved in. And then on the evaluation side, things like opening up peer review, making it more transparent, more interactive, more collaborative, etc. So those are in the range of things, at least to consider. You can't do all of them. But there, there are a lot of possibilities. On the value on the metrics side, I think the real opportunity is leveraging what already exists, which is make each of the outputs assignable unit. This is already an understood and valued way in which people take scholarship seriously. And simple things like make attach DUIs, to scholarly outputs that are not just papers is an easy, low hanging fruit way to do this. And services like the OSF where's the nodo offer that already has capabilities for making these things more, more integrated into reward systems? Thank you.

Monica Granados 1:42:45

I kind of want to tie the first bullet in the second bullet. We've talked a lot about physical access to information and, and data. And what about like the interpretability? Or the easy to understand aspect of science? What if we talked a little bit, you know, beyond that research cycle, maybe into sort of the knowledge mobilization and talk about plain language summaries as an example, it would be great to have some training on plain language summaries. Or even if you have like a Bureau of science communicators who are trained in translating peer reviewed literature into plain language summaries, that would be very cool investment. Because as we understand, I know scientists and researchers are stretched very thin and probably don't have the time or the present incentives to do that. And so if there was a bureau that they you know, they could work with to translate their knowledge into something that was that had a plain language summaries, you could you know, attach that to a peer reviewed publication to make it more than just physically accessible. Also easy to understand.

chelle gentemann 1:43:58

This sounds like an AI ml project that could go horribly wrong or horribly, right.

Monica Granados 1:44:03

Yeah. That's what we do for translations. I always start with like, when, when I translate even when I translate to Spanish, which is my like, mother tongue, I let the machine do the first the first pass. It's worth thinking about.

chelle gentemann 1:44:18

Yeah. It's, at least for me, I found it incredibly helpful when I'm thinking about complex scientific problems, to try and talk to everybody. I like that plain language summaries. It's one of the hardest things to do because we're not trained in it. So yeah, I love the idea of trying to create resources around that. Thank you.

Yvonne Ivey 1:44:39

You know, one of the questions Fernando had earlier was like, what are the challenges we've been facing? And one of the ones that our teams has been grappling with is, how do we actually focus on the A accessibility and DIA and so one of the first steps we took was making our slides accessible for Um, you know, ensuring that when we have either graphics or videos, we use alt text, like trying to do like have, you know, like a requirement for all of our slide decks so that we're removing those barriers. And I think sort of the plain language summaries, when we talk to our science communicators, I think that's something valid, we should bring up. You know, we're doing all text for all of our images on our website, why aren't we actually breaking down all of the reports that are on our website, like doing those small sets to show that we're moving forward and trying to make progress?

1:45:35

I am actually occur, by the way. My apologies. That's okay. No worries. It's a very ambiguous name could be male or female. And I just wanted to expand on my point. I think it kind of relates to teaching what I wrote, I don't know if you can actually see the comments or not. It was in terms of like teaching, open scholarship leadership. If you're in a situation where you want to do open science, but nobody really above you, has training. It's one thing if people train, how to use, you know, open code, or anything else for their own research. Another thing is if you know, their training, how to lead a team

doing that. And they feel it's really somehow debilitating when the people above you can't really lead the team in this way, not because they don't want to, but because they don't know how. So I think probably concentrating on that will be a good idea. In terms of lab lab leads, and yeah, PRs, that kind of stuff.

Yvonne Ivey 1:47:10

Thank you. And if it's okay, Monica, I want to go back to you because someone asked a question in the chat. Yeah. So, Kevin, I don't know if you want to come off mute, or I can read your question for you. Can you hear me? Yep.

1:47:29

Yeah, I guess I'm just curious. Yum. You mentioned this concept of having sort of this bureau creating plain language summaries. And it just made me think of what are other sort of channels for communicating that out to a wider audience like a public? And it's not the only way, of course, because we want it to be the most accessible, but one method was, would it be useful to say, establish partnerships, if such a bureau existed with like different public news organizations that probably already have some people doing science and, you know, sort of science reporting? Maybe that's something that they would, you know, they would feel like they can then transition into their publication for wider distribution. I don't know if that would be useful or not. But

Monica Granados 1:48:13

yeah, that would be this mark. Again, that would be incredibly useful to have that pipeline, usually, to build that kind of pipeline, and we're dealing with this a bit of the open climate campaign is that you have to create relationships with the with, either with an organization that can facilitate a connection with a journalist, or you already have an existing relationship with it with a journalist, but that's something that the bureau could do. And then I would add an additional level that it would be great if they anything that produced was CCP license, because organizations like the conversation is a great place where people publish, and then other news outlets can just remix and reuse the publication from the conversation because it's openly licensed. So you know, we would facilitate sort of spreading that out more to your point, right is to make it easier for those plain language summaries to to be disseminated as far and wide as possible.

chelle gentemann 1:49:12

I came up with a name for the Bureau. It can be the plain language, open summaries plos last. Name quite behind and we do want comments on a year of open science. So what I'm going to recommend is if you have other comments, put them in chat so we can capture them. And then we're going to move to the era of open science. Is that okay? Yeah, we have an open discussion this afternoon. And we have lots more to say this is perfect. This is exactly what we were hoping for. So thank you. It gives her many advantages to this. I think we're gonna just skip those. We'll provide the slide deck to you. There's some other places where we have questions. We want to hear more about this global equity, you know, equitable access to science. And maybe we can table that for an afternoon discussion, because that is not our 32nd discussion.

Yvonne Ivey 1:50:42

The suggestion is to rename all of our coffee breaks to tops tea. Oh, that's cute. Oh, motor joke.

1:50:57

smart and funny.

Yvonne Ivey 1:51:00

All right, so we're gonna jump into the year of open science activities and partnerships. So what is the year of open science? NASA is designated 2023, the year of open science. And during that year, we'll be focused on not only meeting guards three KPIs, but also accelerating all of our plans, through the yearbook and science. So what does that look like? Having high visibility at all large society meetings, putting out publications and articles, he is working on an Open Science Award, as well as those virtual cohorts. We mentioned summer schools and in doing three marquee events, which are targeted workshops at MSL minority serving institutions or emphasize a lot of this work is already in motion. As you can imagine, we're kicking off the year of open science at AMS in January. And so we have a lot of work in the next couple of months to ensure that we're set up for success. So I'm going to dive a little deeper into how we're going to roll out the year both in science for 2023 Spin core will be online and independent at for folks who learn in different manner. So whether you're you want to work in a cohort, or you would like to just kind of sit at home and do this or through various in person workshops, and all the large conferences will be rolling out that curriculum, as I shared will be at 12 large society meetings and the society meetings or the science societies that NASA typically attends. Those societies will be across Earth, and space and Life Sciences will be hosting some hackathons as well as some open science events. We're looking into various models of success. I would love feedback on things that y'all have found successful throughout your various activities. But we found that to truly train folks up on open science, we're looking into a hackathon. So Wikipedia advance as those sorts of fun activities to engage not only undergrads, but graduate students and postdocs, but also some of the senior scientists that might be interested in training up with some data science skills. We are priority prioritizing events and not our one minority serving institutions. We last week, we were in Howard having several conference Parent University, which is located in Washington, DC, having several conversations with their research Provost to learn a little bit about what they have coming up in 2023. They actually have a research month, which is every April, and they bring all of their students together to talk about all the research that they're doing. So we're looking you know, James, Jim, rather, you've mentioned earlier the car we actually activating this, and what are we doing that's practical, but also intentional, trying to have more of those conversations with those folks who are at minority serving institutions that have these programs that we can truly build that sort of pathway into NASA Science. Sharing knowledge resources, so leveraging our GitHub, we said earlier, having that call coming out and actually asking folks to get involved, but also having these types of conversations. I knew about shells grant being out in the open, but I didn't realize it was an open grant. So being able to have this conversation so that everyone is kind of on the same page, but also going to those same resources. And then we're putting out a call for moonshots. Our 2024 activities that were lining up, which is the science for our MOOC extensions, as well as more hackathons and events, we'll be kicking off the moonshot goals. Again, continue to prioritize events and not our one minority serving institutions, as well as sharing that knowledge resource So in true fashion, we love to put together a plan. So again, this kind of drills into some of the activities that we'll be doing in 2023. In a more visual manner.

1:55:13

There's a question in the chat room.

Yvonne Ivey 1:55:16

So would you like to take the question on moonshot? What does it mean?

chelle gentemann 1:55:22

Why do you think moonshot I need? I guess we actually have, we get this question half the time when we say moonshot. What we are talking about is a high risk, high reward scientific activity, we want to enable Open Science at scale to solve big challenges. And so we're going to be having a call to do exactly that. We want open science teams to approach problems and new ways to solve really difficult problems and try to make breakthroughs.

brooks hanson 1:55:58

I just want to highlight that the word is invented because of what happened at NASA, who actually went to the moon. In my lifetime, I love

Yvonne Ivey 1:56:10

Thank you. Thank you, Bree. And so we've been getting a lot of questions around what conferences will be at. So you can see our lovely table, which highlights all of the conferences that we'll be at, as well as sort of the equation of why we're showing up for these 12 caucuses. We obviously want to hit every science discipline within NASA science, but also focus on historically underrepresented groups, conferences, particularly the Society of Asian scientists and engineers, the American Indian science and engineers conference, sadness, as well as those focus hackathons at minority serving institutions, we really want to cast a wide net, and also be as inclusive as possible through our focus activities. But then, since just those 12 Priority events, we plan to be in many other places. And I say that as keflings out the room. Because we want to be as visible as possible, but engaged with as many folks as possible as well. I will note that all of these conferences, as well as the other ones that aren't priority, we have a link on our GitHub that you can follow along with us. But also you can submit where you'll be so that if you need Topps materials or if you're interested in teaching open core, I when we roll out sort of the train to train, train our model, we want folks to know where we'll be, but also to share with us growth there'll be this is also our plan of meeting 20,000 scientists and researchers. So I'm here, I really want to shift into sort of our open discussion around the gaps in our plan. One of the things that our team talks about very frequently, we don't want to do this in a silo, nor in a vacuum. So we need sort of some support to make sure that we aren't missing anything. So we have some prompts on the slide to get folks talking. Also for our virtual panelists, you'll see the link, which should be available in the chat as well, where folks can engage on our IO tool, which is an interactive tool where you can submit questions and feedback. But some of the prompts we have, you know, is holding a half day meeting at a large busy meeting. So those 12 Priority workshops and conferences that we mentioned a good strategy. Like we want you to put yourself in the shoes, would you step out of a large conference for a half day workshop to take open for? Next prompt? What are some other strategies to reach 20,000? Scientists and researchers who are open science batch, like what have you found helpful in getting books either take your trainings or curriculum but also use your materials. Next up, we have some users are already using Open edX and the certification process will be automatic. And also the learning

experience will be consistent across the platform. So whether you're in person or virtual, or doing it from your laptop, by yourself, we want this to be consistent across the board. So are you finding that in person workshops with materials online and available will actually be successful and useful? Another problem we have should we have minimal requirements for events offered tops badges, and what should those requirements be? You know, going back to Fernando's question, like what are the challenges, you know, how do we set up this criteria and requirements for this batch? You know, we found that although NASA has done a lot, it's not the certification process. It's one of the things we've got that for this type of batch. And then lastly, What other minimum requirements should we have when it comes to getting folks engaged in open science? What have you found to be best practices or positive practices across your organizations?

chelle gentemann 2:00:10

And we want to recognize and discuss. Anytime you add a requirement, you add a barrier. So how do we like where's that balance between making sure that you know, these in person event that things are available and accessible? And that people can get certified that this can go anywhere? And anybody can get certified? Do we need to have that minimum requirement? And how do we sort of like think about that, but we could just maybe start at the top and have comments or people can jump in wherever they want? We'll go this way that's.

Malvika Sharan 2:00:52

So if it's only for the first question, I think you might need to consider a free event workshop rather than three. Yeah, I think share has done loads of that. People don't want to get out of the conference at like dinners. That always helps. And I think dinners are actually one of the places where people get to talk about where the relevance of topics they learned. And where does that apply. One point that I wanted to really bring up, which actually applies to most of these questions. And I think Marshall is here for that reason, is championship Network Development. identifying people who are already doing some work the work that you need to train them to actually champion the knowledge and Marshall, thank you for being here. Another point around. Champions is also let's not define open science for everybody, give them the framework, ask people to define what openness means to them. Oftentimes, when I I talk to people, I would actually show things that they might already be into already doing. So bring this exhaustive list of things which says this is what open science is, do you identify one or two things that you will redo, you're actually an open scientist come and join the champions network or so I think you need to invest on people who are already doing the work because you need to develop impact in the first year, show the evidence, and then it will expand, right? So first year, you can really focus on people where you don't need to convince them too hard, where they're already doing the future of work. So it also gives them you know, the badging could be starting from their thinking, not really putting the requirement because they're already fitting that whole criteria system. And I love the idea that let's not recognize individual as individual champions network of champions.

Monica Granados 2:02:48

I'll just add one thing to Belleek aside from the Creative Commons perspective, we have a similar strategy where we're going to go to some major conferences to talk about the open climate campaign. And it makes me wonder whether or not we should team up at some of these things, right and share resources so that you're paying 50% of whatever it's going to cost us to do these things. And so we can

beat people because nothing gets people out like free food, or it still works still works on me. So so I'm sure Creative Commons is probably another like organizations that have like funding in a similar strategy. And like, let's figure out how we can kind of like, Let's do triple A s together.

Yvonne Ivey 2:03:26

Yeah, yeah. One of the things when we began to talk to many of the societies, and we were like, what, bring students into the workshop, and they were like, just providing Coca Cola and chips,

SherAaron Hurt 2:03:44

I'd say a couple of things. So for holding the half day workshops at basic competence, while definitely you want to do a free event, it is so vital and key that you have buy in from the organization itself. With the carpenters, we tried to do that on several occasions. Sometimes it works, sometimes it doesn't. What I found is when we are when it's early on, and there is a common ground, to organize the conference organizers understand that way that they're promoted to it is if it's not a part of their promotional, you know, their promotional strategy, we can be doing all we want to do to promote it to our people. But if it's not in their promotional material, it goes downhill. And that's happened to us on several occasions. So it's very, very key. If they do have that, I'm starting to see that a lot of conferences are starting to do pre the live workshops the first couple of days in the actual conference the next day. So just check those out. Again, making sure that you are part of that promotional material, because if not, it'll get missed. Then as it relates to shoot, we will jump in down should we have minimum requirements for events, I do believe that there should be some type of minimum, this and I say that one because when you have a requirement, it gives value to that too. thing that we're doing and also value to the people that are doing and when I think about the carpentries. And a lot of times we tell people, you can make your event free your workshop free. However, when people pay a little bit of something, not necessarily monetary, but when they have to do something, there's more buy in. And so it makes more value for that person. But also as the, you know, instructors or as the persons that are going to be, you know, putting on the workshop for people that are going to be doing these summer classes, or even taking the time to review these things. You don't want to be reviewing just mediocre work, where it's like, Oh, someone just threw something together, you know, like, why am I wasting my time reviewing this stuff. So I do believe, while it does not have to be, you know, too high to achieve, there needs to be some type of minimal, minimal requirements that we can discuss later.

brooks hanson 2:05:49

2023 is the 75th anniversary of the digital era. So the transistor was invented. and information theory was invented 75 years ago, this year of open science is really the kickoff of the century of open science. And I feel like this gaps in the plan. when looked at from that lens, there are a lot of gaps. So I don't see the National Science Foundation up there. I don't see NIH up there. I know that UNESCO has got a big strategy. But is there buy in from these other organizations in these badges? I understand that the badges may play a role in NASA funding, will NSF make funding contingent upon an accomplishment in the open court? I triple E will probably be an interesting partner in this. I think a lot of the things that we're excited about what we call open is really the use of digital tools to facilitate virtual communities to collaborate in new ways. And therefore we're really working in the wake of the 1947 1948. And this miraculous of, you know, Shockley and Bardeen, and and Shannon and others, I worry that the badges are a bit of a convenient proxy that you can count someone who's completed the badge, does that

mean that they're going to produce the other return on investments like the major breakthroughs? Or is this just something that you can easily count and therefore measure and then present back a return on investment. So I feel like the badges are a little bit too front and center until you validated that badge, open scientists are outperforming other scientists. And without that justification, I worry that these \$40 million are going to be devoted towards creating badged open scientists, instead of changing the way that humans understand the world. And so I just worry a little bit about the focus on badges. My last comment on badges, which kind of echoes what I said before, is, I recommend that you use a federated strategy. So there should be many entities that can deploy the curriculum and validate I mean, if you really want to get to 20k, you're going to have to use a network effect. And I liked that there's an open edX platform, but I know that there will be people that will be hesitant to use Open edX. And if you can, instead, make it very easy for someone at one of these Society events, to embed open core curriculum in whatever they're doing, without sending someone else to another place. And to go through and Open edX and do all of this stuff, then that federated approach allows for these skills to be trained by others deployed by others assessed by others according to the criteria, and then you'll get to 20k faster. So those are a few more words.

chelle gentemann 2:08:30

Can I ask you to expand a little bit on? So we've talked about, you know, all of the materials are sort of twofold. There's the online massive online course. So that material, there's in person workshop materials, which are like slides and scripts, sort of like what the carpentries provides for their in person workshops. What would make it easier to embed those resources? Like how should we be providing those are there? Is there a certain format? Is there a certain technology that would make this easier for other people to use? What do you suggest?

brooks hanson 2:09:05

Sure. So I'd really like this to be deployed as a repo that can be launched. Like, for example, if it's a, if it's a CMS that I can put in a folder underneath my conference website. And there's a couple places where I can drop the brand for my conference into it. So it looks like NASA plus whatever I'm running, so if it looked like a website that I can launch, as part of my way of communicating with the folks that I want to work with that would help. And then I also understand that you have some interactivity. So maybe there's a way to make that Open edX platform into this CMS that I'm talking about. But give this to instructors or organizers as a resource that they can mix and match and adjust and then deploy to their art. audiences customized to their audience's needs, obviously have constraints around that. Because you don't want somebody to take, you know, the 1/3. That is perhaps the least important to NASA, and then claim certification on that. So there have to be some boundaries on the use, but make this something that can be deployed in my world rather than causing asking me to ask my audience to go over here to open edX to do this. It's not that I think that that's a bad strategy. It's just that I want to, I know that they're going to be organizers who want to kind of control the content that their conference participants are working on. And you can mobilize more quickly that way by facilitating Federation's. So I'm going to try and explain.

Kevin Murphy 2:10:39

You have a good example of one of these.

brooks hanson 2:10:44

So let's see, I think a good example, I mean, I'm relying back on a content management system. Yeah. So so when I want to build, I mean, everybody for a while the range wants to use this academic theme for the evening. So he's got a website, many people have websites built on the academic theme. But there's a subtle emphasis on what's important in the way that an academic represents herself in the way that that CMS is phrased. So if we had a similar CMS with the outlines, and the structure, headings, and invitations for, you know, in your community of cryosphere research, you can add here, so it looks more like a structured core into which you can add other pieces. So the framework becomes a subtle expression of expectations around open science, but it provides a facility for discipline specific customization. I can think more about other examples, but the sort of like the thing that I worry about in the conversation about, for example, the publishers, I'm kind of reminded of that as well. If you go back to 1996, and you look at the wave of the internet, and you're a publisher, and now I asked you to think like a for profit, venture capital funded entrepreneur, what can we do with this thing for science. So what we did was, we built all of these companies, and put the PDFs behind paywalls and made bank. So we're in a transition now, similar to 1996, where I think the future of science is going to involve these interactive notebook publications, different ways to bring junior collaborators into contact with senior collaborators who might be in different countries. So there are for profit entrepreneurs right now, trying to figure out how they can make money off the enterprise of science. And I think we should be thinking similarly, like entrepreneurs, not with for profit, but with a different objective function. How can we ensure that the new technology that's facilitating changes in science is deployed in such a way that the goals of science are advanced? And I'm not sure that we're thinking that way? At the scope of the plan? Because the impact of the Open Science Initiative that NASA has catalyzed is much, much bigger than NASA. And this, the gaps in the plan, the biggest gap in the planet is the other entities that are really incentivizing and pushing science forward are not on that slide. And I think that's, that's my main gap.

Kevin Murphy 2:13:21

Like, I agree with you, I think that, you know, we've been fortunate at NASA to have leadership that agrees with this, and wants to make it public. And it's been difficult to get that same lady with the exception of maybe NIH, the same push in that direction. So that's some work we've got to do. And I think we're trying to work with OSTP. On on getting that support. But yeah, that that was one of our big known gaps. And I think it's not only the other funding agencies, it's that we recognize that the community has been existent, longer even then the funding agencies recognition, but it was fine. So I fully agree with their

brooks hanson 2:14:11

and I hope my comments about this are not meant to be critical of NASA, the NASA leadership is here. I'm here because I absolutely believe in this mission right now. But I think that the absence of other scientific communities that aren't funded by NASA is something to be noted. You know, I frequently go back one of my favorite documents is the Endless Frontier, this document that really defined the modern era of science funding by Van der Bush. And if you look through that, with the lens of tops, there are many different sections where you can see that Bush's argument for why the United States Government should massively invest in science following the world war two effort. Many of the themes anticipate the openness he talks about talent development. He talks about the need to mobilize knowledge faster, and to address the issue. issues of national security concern and intellectual property

aspects around that. So the government that listened to Bush is probably very similar to the government that's listening to Kevin and chelle and understanding how to reference the historical reasons why science is funded in that pioneering argument. And why now is a new time to look at science in a different way. I think there's just a lot to learn from that. That text. Yeah. All right. Thank you.

chelle gentemann 2:15:31

Both directly, I think the very first document that I sent you about tops had Vandermeer Busch quote at the top of Brian has a

isabella martinez 2:15:42

very long insightful comment in the chat. And we also have a couple of questions from our virtual audience. And recognizing that we have about seven minutes until we break for lunch, I was wondering if the folks in the room would mind if we turn to our virtual participants more?

Brian Nosek 2:15:58

Well, I shudder for everyone for you having to read it, or me rereading it for everybody. So it's there, I'm happy to elaborate on any of it. The key of observation is to support the idea of broadening the outcome evaluation, but simultaneously making sure that what are the targets are realistic of what the actual intervention could have an impact on, rather than the aspirational ends that are much further from the ability of the current investment to achieve? So that's the basic idea, but I'm happy to respond to any further on it. And nashing, I shouldn't GV

isabella martinez 2:16:56

had a question. Also about the 20 Carry? Let me find it again. One second, please.

Qiusheng Wu 2:17:02

Can I speak? Oh, yes, yes. Yeah, so a lot of a great discussion. And so I like to respond to the some of the questions here are holding a half day workshop. So to me, they may be useful, but I think if you want to have a broader impact compensation is I think it's very limited. I personally hosted work soft competencies, and sometimes they have a capacity like 2030 People like in person. So I would suggest, if possible, develop the materials make them open access. And similarly, you can put them on GitHub and use some Jupiter book to build like, executable books that people can follow during the workshop in conferences, but they can also after because, to me, that goes a lot more beyond just the conference participants because people the timezone differences and also the money issue, they might not be able to travel. So it'd be best to utilize both ways to both in person and also virtual. And so the other way is that once you have those are no books or Jupiter books are built on top of those materials. People, for example, teaching at universities, undergraduate, they can adopt the materials to for the teaching. So in that way, they can pass knowledge that I think tops can can give the guidance best practices, but change the teachers and then the teacher, the teacher students. So in that way, you will reach a much wider audience. So from my personal experience, I teach classes in university, I make all the materials notebooks, and to my class bows on GitHub, so anyone can use that. And also produce videos. So at the end it can do is to 10s of 1000s of people that they are learning by themselves, they are not limited just to the competencies. So in terms of the badges, I think they make the materials free.

And so if you have loads, learning platforms, you can include some additional videos and also some quizzes, whatever. So if they want to obtain for example, Beegees the certificate they need to have some additional requirements by seeing the basic curriculum or the materials can be open access, and anyone can learn any can contribute rather than limited to a specific learning platform. So in a way, it's going to lose a much wider audience. This is from my personal experience. Thank you.

isabella martinez 2:19:48

One last question around this outer shell I feel like this question was mostly aimed at you which is can you explain why 20k Is it like, are there other demographics metrics is that total number important?

chelle gentemann 2:20:05

We came up with 20k. Based on sort of 60,000 members of the earth and space science community around the age you have the numbers and 20k, we thought reaching 1/3 of them would be, there's a lot of evidence around 30% of the community is what you need to sort of that tipping point where it starts to become accessible. And so that's how we came up with the 20k.

Yvonne Ivey 2:20:34

And the reason why we focused on looking at AV use specifically is because it's the largest Earth and space science, open conference, so we wanted to kind of target them specifically,

isabella martinez 2:20:47

speaking for myself, I see the 20k as a minimum,

chelle gentemann 2:20:50

just personally, we do because it's not just age, you it's not, we wanted to have a target that we thought was okay. We wouldn't have a target that we gave to reach, but also a more.

Malvika Sharan 2:21:08

Quickly mentioned, shell, you might have met Angela Brown, good for sentences it fcci. She's a Program Manager for event fund for photosensors society, and I've been working with them for for several years now. And they're doing incredible work in disseminating the small funding, say had one of the features found on the focus on environment. They work with different funders very much in Fernando's point, where can you work with like different philanthropy doing the work and disseminating these small funding data are getting quite a lot of minority universities in the US as well. So I definitely think that would be nice to collaborate with them,

chelle gentemann 2:21:50

that we talked about trying to have a coordinated strategy, or at least, at least a sharing of information and efforts among the different agencies and philanthropic organizations in this area. So that we don't have a situation where larger well funded libraries, keep writing really good proposals and getting funded and there becomes this gap. And I see us all sort of covering different parts of this space. And if we are all aware of what each other's doing, we'll probably do it better.

Fernando Perez 2:22:33

Two quick notes, one, going back a little bit to the discussion about platforms and edX. Full disclosure, both Jim and I are co founders have to wait to see so we're probably biased in that regard. But Twitter is seen as an organization that encoded a specific set of principles in a blog post that someone posted on the website called the right to replicate. And that might be it's a little bit more than being open source, right? It is how do you structure the content? And how do you rely on the fact that the world has existing proprietary tools that you need, like cover AWS, or whatever? So we try and credit goes to you, you know, there's really the the bulk of the right amount that to encode explicitly, how should an organization develop its ideas and its tools. So if they're not just open, but so that the stakeholders have the right to reuse them in a way that empowers them, rather than the Creator. So maybe that could be kind of a principle that tops could like crib often and adopted and whatnot as a guiding principle and number to move in a different direction. I'm wondering if, and I'm just a bit a little bit out of the loop in the conferences of the open source people just for a variety of personal and family reasons. But I'm wondering that this project is leapfrogging in some ways and really, really catalyzing things that have been happening there. And have you gone to the size of the world, the Giulia cons of the world is their active connection with those people. Because I think there's a lot of potential, obviously, in those communities. And if all of that has been done, great, but if not, I think there's value in not only going to the abuse of the world, but also reconnecting with those stories. Sometimes they're a little bit like on the margins of they're kind of despair academics that are surviving on the fringes. So saying, Hey, this is happening now. And we're doing it and rebuilding or building some of those grids. So if it's all been done, great, I've been a little bit out of the loop. But if it hasn't, I think the potential there is humongous. And I know that those people would lap it up,

chelle gentemann 2:24:33

up and I had a big conversation about so Yuvi Panda, if you know him. We had a big conversation about a call to action for a lot of these developers and excellent coders where we could essentially have a call to action to help us work on some of these major problems and these big breakthroughs and really trying to work with them. So I'm giving In a keynote at PI data, New York, Ivana is going to get her universe, we're going to reinvent. So we are trying to get out of this science sphere as much as not within, we can only be in so many places. But again, we really encourage, like, you know, for those people who are attending, we have slides, we have resources, we'll do everything we can to help you share this message of like, science includes you as well, and we want to work with you.

Yvonne Ivey 2:25:34

But I think look at the panel itself. You know, one of the things that we wanted to do with this review panel, is to not only invite subject matter experts, but actually talk to people who have been working in open science. And as we were talking to folks are like, well, there's no one from you know, the specific science domains, we were like, We're building something new, we need the folks who are entrenched in open science to give us feedback and point out things that we've not been thinking about. So I think we're slowly starting to better engage with those communities. But actually, as chelle mentioned, thinking about this call to action, and being more intentional in bringing those folks to those conferences, or showing up at their conferences, because it's one of the things we've really been grappling with, it's like this, the methodology about how to break down barriers, do we invite people into the room? Or do we go to them, and actually going through them? And listening in and asking the

questions that we're grappling with instead of just expecting them to talk to us? We're trying to kind of bring that lens as we're trying to shift the culture

Fernando Perez 2:26:43

put upon Paris, anytime come. You're all invited. birthday present for the

2:26:54

next day. The future scientists of the world

Yvonne Ivey 2:27:02

so that I think we're gonna break for lunch. And also call the AV folks back in the room so that they can help us figure out what the issues are. lunches provided in the room. And for folks on the line. We're going to break for an hour. Thank you.

chelle gentemann 2:27:24

If you want more than that lunch to the cafeteria is right here. Yes. And there's lots of seating.

Cynthia Hall 2:27:43

Hey, sure. All right, everyone. Thanks, Isabella. Another exciting thing that we've been working on is we have been interviewing some NASA scientists, some subject matter experts in open science, many of who were helped us with the open core module development. And we've created success stories. We have them on our GitHub, some are on our GitHub. And then we also have some that are on NASA's science.nasa.gov as blogs. And I will say that Flavio did one and it has been picked up and retweeted many times. And actually a journal called coaching and education or something like that wants to actually republish it. So they're getting a lot of, and we'd love to have more success stories. So we'd love to hear from you all on that. App, as Yvonne was mentioning, and shell mentioning earlier about Space Apps. I wanted to give you some statistics, but we had, we wanted to create some space out challenges. And last weekend, we collaborated with other space agency partners. And this is the largest annual global hackathon. All over the world, we have these three challenges, which they already talked about, so we won't delve into them. I will tell you a little bit more information about each one, we had to create an application using machine learning and artificial intelligence techniques that allowed users to input short text phrases and match that input to NASA science data or imagery, and then display the results for the user in a creative way. So that was turning on stem into steam. We had to develop a had them develop a creative method that used the arts to share and explain the design process under andorre scientific results from NASA research project and that was the art in our worlds. And then we had them look at creating a new metric to have the valuate the effectiveness of open science activities, and that was measuring open science. And again, 1000s of people participated in that activity. So we're really excited about that.

chelle gentemann 2:30:12

What's the schedule for either? Like, what what happens next?

Cynthia Hall 2:30:16

Yeah, so with the Space Apps Challenge it, the community, the community goes through and kind of, there were hundreds of apps developed art not developed their their ideas for development. And they will go through, lead those down to, you know, a select, like 10 or so. And then there will be global judges that go in and rank them, and then there'll be a winner. Yeah, and I think that winner gets to go on and actually develop what they propose. Yeah, it's really cool,

Yvonne Ivey 2:30:47

depending on where they're located. So either be invited to a NASA launch. And or go on and share not only the code and algorithms that they put out from their challenge, but also publicly be able to talk more about the work that they did to support Space Apps.

chelle gentemann 2:31:07

Like one of the art ones that I clicked on, you could take any NASA image, and then pick a favorite artists, and it would turn like the people were doing such cool thing.

Cynthia Hall 2:31:18

Yeah, I honestly, I almost took some of the images that were shared. But then I was afraid we weren't able to do it. Because there were some really cool things that came out of that the these are primarily younger students. And what they create is really inspiring, like next generation, like what we're seeing come out of the space out challenges.

chelle gentemann 2:31:37

And like one of the things with the metric for open science, like we know, there are a lot of metrics for open science. We wanted to reach out to the world and say, Oh, maybe there's things we're not thinking about. And here's this huge community that didn't like, give us Yeah, share their ideas.

Cynthia Hall 2:31:54

Yeah, it was really exciting to be a part of that. And then last, the last slide that I have really is, you know, we really wanted to put ourselves out there a little bit more. So AGU created a Twitter, it's apt to open science, which I'm sure you all have seen. We have a YouTube site now or we're putting all of our recordings. And we also I think you were mentioned in the podcast already, we're working with I triple E to develop that podcast. And actually our listserv has grown from like a couple 100 to 1000s. So that's pretty exciting. Since we started, so growing our community. Cyndi has been talking mostly about the stuff that we've done so far. And I'm gonna pivot a little bit and talk about the stuff we haven't begun yet that we are beginning to prep over the year of open science, and really then pivot into our discussion, which is going to be about how to keep this momentum going, not only during the year of open science, but beyond that, and I know a couple of us started to talk about that during lunch. One of the things that I've been developing along with some of our tops champions, Brian was on the line this morning as Sam was an online community building plan. And why have an online engagement plan we're not an Instagram influencer or something. So it gives learners a forum to ask questions and receive advice from the experts who are already part of our community. We're hoping to build the scaffolding of what will be a community we grow through our open core through the people who take the open core core truly beginners truly just entering the open science community for the first time, and already exists communities like the Turing way and the carpentries. But we also want to have one that's specific to

tops and to kind of the combination and the curation of all these communities in one area. It helps keep people informed. That's how we were using the GitHub to post the agenda as we created it with the latest update being last night. It allows us to distribute our resources to amplify the work that we're doing. The open science stories project was originally on our GitHub before it moved to nasa.science.gov. And now to these other venues, this is exciting. And also when we do when we have an online community, it makes it easier for people to speak up when there's something we're doing wrong. And there's something that we need to adapt and change your bond, would you mind? Thank you. So particularly, I've been thinking a lot about our GitHub and how to get the most out of our GitHub. So we've broken up into three things. We're going to have the blogs and the resources. We're already doing that we're growing that today, I want to have your help doing that with our interactive event later today. We've enabled our GitHub discussions as well as chosen and moderators and created a code of conduct moderation plan in order to have discussions and then we're going to be using the GitHub issues in order for people to point to things that we already have up there or things you've already done. to ask for improvements or changes. So hopefully your discussions to be that place of kind of like seamless, less moderated discussion, although we will be posting topics which I'll get to in a second, we'll issues is really about the, your, this resource is up, and there's either something wrong with it or it needs to be expanded or at this other person, you should come look at this page. So in order to go along with our in person engagement, both Yvonne and Sydney have talked about all the conferences we're gonna be at, we really want people who are able to be at that conference to still know what we're up to. And also, they're going to be off weeks, thank goodness between the conferences, and we want people to know that we're still thinking about important topics during that time. So moving forward, beginning in November, and then through the entire year of open science, we're going to have four blog posts per month, each of which are going to have two associated discussions, and one associated polls. Some of the polls, I hope to be funny. There was one that I wanted to do in honor of the collaboration plan that the Artemis mission has posted publicly online, just a poll that says Apollo or Artemis, not substantive Devall. But I also want to have polls that are more serious like the one that we had for our community forum on the open core, which we're about once we posted the open core, what is the area where you're most excited to learn, and what's the area that you're most daunted by like pools where we can gather information, and then the discussion posts, which will allow for people to chime in to whatever we talked about in the blog, weeks with conferences, we're going to talk about what we're doing at that conference, highlight our partners and collaborators, well off, we will be themed to such open science. I just mentioned, the Artemis session, so on and so forth. I want to show you that I put all

Yvonne Ivey 2:36:41

the themes in the deck, I'm not gonna go through

isabella martinez 2:36:44

them all, if you want to go through either volunteer for a guest blog, or suggest a topic that you think we should look into and include as part of this kind of formal programming, please let me know, as I said, this is really meant to fill in the gaps in the month and week that we're not at conferences, actively working to show the areas that we're thinking of, again, beyond the year of open science,

chelle gentemann 2:37:04

there's two sides of this. So you could just click twice. Thank you. Yeah. And we're really happy to highlight other like, right, again, this is about platforming visibility. So, you know, you were just talking earlier about ways that we can, you know, provide visibility to a lot of the open science community. And this is another spot that

2:37:23

we can do that. Exactly.

isabella martinez 2:37:29

Right. So that moves very nicely. And I think right on time, into the gaps in our plan. So what we'll want to know is what gaps exist in our community outreach and engagement plans, particularly who do you think we're not reaching? What discussions and collaborations would you like to see take place which we began talking a little bit before lunch? And also, how should we participate in existing open science communities? So the latter two, I'm really happy that we already began talking about. So I would love to spend a little bit of time on Who are we not reaching? And how do you think we reach them? And how do we make more of the community that hasn't been a part of open science conversations in the past, part of Topps is community outreach and engagement. And then if it's not too much trouble, maybe we can actually display the jam board while we had this conversation. So virtual participants. We have a jam board. It's a nice kind of display. I'm going to put that link in the chat so it's easier to access. And we are excited to kick off our conversation this afternoon with this very important topic.

Yvonne Ivey 2:38:38

folks in the room, first question, what gaps in your opinion exists in our community outreach and engagement plan? Yes.

Fernando Perez 2:38:47

So I don't know if it's exactly a gap. But I first of all, I really appreciate how thoughtful, you've been about it. And there's there's a lot of wonderful stuff in there. But I'm wondering, this is based on feedback that we've received and the Jupiter community, about the way we work is that as as much as I am a fan of GitHub, and we use it for everything and can live in there. There are communities that do find GitHub to be a barrier, right. And specifically, in our context, what has come up often is people who are very design centric tend to operate with workflows, just the tool chains that they use are tend to be different from from a GitHub centric workflow. And obviously, there's the element of some by Microsoft, it's a single company, and so on and so forth. And now, obviously, there's a lot of this that kind of needs to be on GitHub, and it makes sense. But I'm wondering too, there's pieces of this where you could potentially Think for example, on Jupiter, we don't use GitHub discussions almost at all. What we do have is a central discourse, instance right discourse or jupiter.org that has topics topical channels for various things education, science, etc. Security, notebooks, etc. You And that as the feel of a more kind of normal web forum that just about anybody who's on the internet has to use, it doesn't require a specific get. I mean, you do have to make a login. But isn't a GitHub login? There's no association with a software development tool. And I'm wondering if you might want to consider a little bit of that just to open up? Do you have a NASA tops domain, like a single domain? NASA topstar. Org? Is that has that been taken? Or managed ticket? Right? Just so that know that? You can do that at this course that talks.nasa.com.

2:40:41

Is there any committee the whole group?

chelle gentemann 2:40:45

Is there any forum like discourse that merges well, with GitHub discussions so that you can actually it's interoperable? The question?

Fernando Perez 2:40:55

I don't know the answer wherever they

chelle gentemann 2:40:57

want. And it'll look, you know, it just, it's the same information just differently presented,

Fernando Perez 2:41:01

I could imagine that being possible to basically create an interoperability two way channel with given that GitHub does have API's for just about everything, but I don't know that that exists.

Malvika Sharan 2:41:13

I able to actually challenge always talking in open, I don't really think that open science, practices are all about doing everything in open, you need to create safer space for people. So it might not be for example, you do have slack, right? Like where people can have this conversation, it is not out in public gives people a lot more comfort in sharing what they want to share. And I don't think everything needs to be open. So I think you need to probably define, Where would people have security, maybe not all people want to be in open meetings like this, because they don't feel like they work, their work needs to be taken out of context. So I would really define when when do you restrict the conversation, in another part, have lots of soil probably not share all of them. But challenge in we invite challenge from NASA community about data very similar to what the art Art Forum was. So people can suggest that here's my data problem, I can't solve it, and you bring people to solve that problem. But give them the framework, which aligns with open source practices like version control data management plan, and so on. And and we do have some examples, I'm happy to share afterwards on that. I think what's really missing is transparency of process. So we say these are the goals that we want to do. This is what we want to achieve. But we don't really ever say how will we maintain the transparency as we develop them? I really admire that you're you're willing to fail in public. I think that's really, really strong, but also demanding for people to be kinder to you, right? Like how you're defining that. Because you all are going to work really hard, it's going to hurt when people would say, Oh, you're not doing it sufficiently? Well, how would you allow people to actually step in to solve those problems? So another point on the community building itself? I don't think a lot of people would want to be part of community community, right? Like they would come for a reason, and they'll leave when they have to leave. So I think you need to really think about for the moment that they are here, how do I recognize their contribution? How do I give them the voice? How do I give them the ownership, so they see their own work, even if they have left? So you want these people to go away, but be champions of the work that you do. So I really would say don't really just focus on keeping these people together, empowering them in a way that they can go wherever they want to do afterwards. But they always have reason to show that this is what I

did. And this is this is what it is. So how does the recognition happen? Maybe you know, there's lots that we can also share about you know, how to incentivize or how to recognize, but I would really recommend about process transparency.

Yvonne Ivey 2:43:56

It was almost as if you were at dinner with us last night, because we talked about how, and if it's okay, if I share we were talking about, like engaging on Twitter, and how a lot of the science community is active in that space. Our team specifically, I tell everyone, I do not understand Twitter, and I think that's probably for the best. So I avoided like the plague. But one of the things we need to really begin thinking about is that kindness piece, like when we're going out and if we're being honest with ourselves, we're asking people to stop working in the way they've been working for decades. And reimagine the way they work. Like we're asking them to like flip the table and be okay with that small amount of chaos, but we're bringing policies and mandates and support and resources. Most people are like, Absolutely not the Thank you. And so how do we build not only mutual respect and understanding but also So, arm ourselves in this like, delicate line of asking folks to listen to us and say that like there's a need for diversity, inclusion and accessibility in science, when most folks are like, but we like that's not what science is. So we were talking through last night, like, what are we going to do when we're faced with? You know, like, we're like, and I think most folks in the room know, shell shows like, what am I going to do? Like, I don't want people to attack, you know, like, I don't get to hide my dual identity. I'm a black woman, like, I don't get to show up and say, I'm just a woman today or like, today, nope, I'm black like, no, no, like, these are things that we need to begin thinking about. Because we're asking people to show up as their authentic selves. And my like, eyes, I view that as what open sciences, like we're asking folks to rethink the way that they're working, but also be authentic in your work, and show up so that other folks can

2:46:01

enjoy that piece.

Malvika Sharan 2:46:03

Just to add that you need I mean, we need to demand respect, that open science isn't a cherry on the top, it's, it's an integration, but what you're saying is for their benefit, their value, but at the same time, they need to recognize the hard work that you're doing. And you need to just, I don't know, I can't say just own that space. But we need to demand respect work.

Yvonne Ivey 2:46:27

It's something that I think as a team, we're we're into internally and externally grappling with. Um, excuse me,

isabella martinez 2:46:37

sorry, request from someone that we all identify ourselves with speaking, which I thought was a good request. So now, Vico is just speaking, and then moving forward. If everyone could say who they are, I think that that would be great. And then also, tennis had their hand raised for a while if you do not mind.

Pen-Yuan Hsing 2:46:57

Thank you. I'm sorry, I just feel that I said probably should have typed it onto the board that you're sharing on your screen right now. So something flashed by really quickly, when you were going through the slides earlier that I noticed, which is, I think it's one of the things that you've identified for. Maybe it was one of the blog posts where the discussions were, it was something about like the history of science, and how did it become closed in a way that it is right now? Something along those lines? I don't know if I'm remembering that correctly. And oh, yes, history lesson. Why do we have close science in the first place? So that that made me think of many things. So first of all, there were both, you know, parts of science that were closed and open compared to right now, historically. And and if you look outside, kind of like the Western traditions, there are even more interesting discussions to be had. But but but I think I have two points about this. One is that I think this kind of fundamental reflection is useful to at least have some reflection on the nature of science itself. Because I think that kind of reflections will give us a lot of really important fundamental motivations for doing open science, in addition to the practical benefits that open science can bring us right. So I think it is important to have that point. And I'm really glad to see this as one of the things but on top of that, the word history also reminds me that I know along with the tremendous creativity that you just talked about, through a lot of the events already done. I think there's an angle for people outside of the natural scientist of sciences to participate in this process as well, right, including people from the arts and humanities. And I'm curious about whether there's an opportunity here to develop more, you know, engagement on that side of things. Hopefully, that makes sense. Oh, I see. Okay. You spoke about that during lunch. And I wish I could be there with you to talk about this. But I'm just thinking because there's so many people I've met, you know, over the years, they're like, No, I'm not a scientist, or I don't care about this. So it has nothing to do with me. And I think when it comes to open science is a huge part of it, is addressing this, right, so I'm just doing this out there as something for us to think about. Thank you.

brooks hanson 2:49:34

So do you know what they call Italian food in Italy? Oh, I'm sorry. My name is Jim coriander, and I'm here from UBC into ITC. So do you want to call Italian food in Italy? They call it food. And you call it digital research in science. It's called research. And I think if we're successful with tops, we will stop saying open because it's just is going to be the new way that we do science. And down the road, a scientist will not necessarily look like me, but will look like Yvonne. And that's the future we're trying to move towards. What I worry about on the gap in the engagement plan is it looks like you're creating a safe space called the top space where people who might feel ostracized from the disciplines that they work in, feel safe. But if we build spaces for a bunch of champions to get together, we will not transform the culture in the communities where right now people feel unsafe. And so this comes back to this federation idea. I think that instead of building online engagement plans for a Topps branded safe space, we need to do the harder work to figure out how to make open science activities take place in the scientific channels outside. So I have two specific observations there. The first is that I suggest that you engage with Institute's so I'm thinking about saying the Mathematical Sciences Research Institute in Berkeley, or the Pacific Institute for the mathematical sciences that I used to work at. They run programs every week. And those programs could potentially, if the institute's leadership chooses to follow this plan, they could take one of these open core units and choose to embed it in their programs. And if they do that, then the leadership within the institutes within disciplines endorses the idea. And so now the postdocs and the graduate students get coverage, because leaders within the discipline are telling the PIs in the discipline that this is important according to the institute's. So I think you can find

new leverage by finding a way to engage with Institute's that run programs like the workshops that you're planning to run all the time. And the second one is, recall correctly, the NSF pkce award has an outreach component. So if it's 1%, or 2%, so maybe you could do something similar in grants outside of Tom's or outside of specifically open science themes in NASA if you get a big grant. I mean, NASA is world class world leader in terms of outreach and scientific engagement. But maybe there's a way to get the scientists that are leading these projects, to figure out how they can tell their story around what they're doing in an open way. So once again, my main theme that I'm harping on this morning and now is to find ways to take the openness, transformation and embedded in the noun that we're trying to transform. We're not building a new now we're adapting and transforming a pre existing

2:52:25

monetary Granada's.

Monica Granados 2:52:32

I'm a little worried about the question of, of who are we not reaching? And this is more from a logistical standpoint, because I'm dealing with the same problem with the open climate campaign. You folks have a very big budget, and you you have a long time frame is it is it four years or five years, okay. But even with that, I'm wondering if it's would be helpful to define the problem space, or at least the stakeholders that you want to reach, I think that you're doing a really good job of getting all of this feedback and seeing who else you can reach, but you also have limited time and limited funds. And I think everybody understands that. And, you know, I worry about that for, you know, the the project that I'm running, because we want to reach as many people as possible and talk to as many people as possible, but there's only one, there's only one staff, you know, for this project, and you folks are also, you know, limited in your capacity. So I wonder if it was just, you know, like, just be forthright about, like, who your stakeholders are, this is who we're going to concentrate on because that I think will set you up more likely for for success because you will meet the needs of these identified stakeholder groups instead of like trying to spread yourself too thin and saying just like okay, this is the problem fix this is what we're going to work on. Otherwise, yeah, I think you you might jeopardize your, your, your mission.

Fernando Perez 2:53:56

This is Fernando Perez, from UC Berkeley and where to see and Jupiter curious and this was already actually brought up by by Penn. But I want to dig a little bit further into the social sciences and the humanities side also from a disciplinary perspective, because I remember when we started so I was one of the people who set up the Berkeley Institute for data science about 10 years ago at UC Berkeley with funding from morons loan donations, and they were very adamant and that we include ethnographers in the design of that institute right in from the very beginning. We had ethnographers these are people who, as a disciplinary training and research area, they study the creation and construction of scientific communities. Right. And they were embedded in the process. They participated they were funded researchers in the in some of my most interesting interactions came from working with those people and from getting to understand the language and the perspective that they brought into the research and they saw them are very interesting in that they kind of they learned to be both participant and observers simultaneously. And that is very much the ethos of their discipline. But there's a lot to be learned. And I realized that NASA is an agency, which is mostly concerned with like the natural sciences of the physical world. But at the same time, every conversation about tribal lands

by environmental justice, etc, is going to effectively be using the language of those disciplines. And I think it would be useful to have those participants, these are entire intellectual traditions with with entire departments and colleges that that do that. And so just a suggestion from the gaps. Event.

Malvika Sharan 2:55:34

Last week, we got here, I absolutely love what Fernando is saying. And in the last six months, I've been working with an ethnographer by practice, but she's a community manager and the children great, and Lee steel, and she has been doing auditing of the project. And as a person who's never been involved in a project coming in three years later, making me see things that I have been doing. But you know, we don't have time, we don't slow down and take note of that. I love that idea very, very much. And we just recently, just last night, we got funding to hire a full time ethnographer. And I'm talking to Chris hold graph to learn more about that ethnographer practice, because I absolutely love that. And I wonder if there is no position full time, you could probably build a residency program, bringing people every year, different people, different people doing ethnography, because what happens with that is that people build their own understanding. So these ethnographer could be literally from the NASA researchers who are just interested in ethnography. But yeah, thank you for raising

Yvonne Ivey 2:56:44

other comments in the room or online? So I'll take the orange. So if you

chelle gentemann 2:56:57

I don't know that link?

2:57:02

Yeah, so

chelle gentemann 2:57:04

in the jam board, so what do you mean by the orange? Yeah, so I think he's gonna share the jam board. Some people have put comments in. This is Chelle gentemann. On the jam board, there is a comment that says, I don't see the rest of the world in this open access plan. There are references to the Beijing Declaration care and fair throughout today's presentation. But I don't see World Data Systems CO data go fair or the DA, RDA in the community outreach slides. These are the stakeholders building the Open Science platforms and policies. So where are they in your

2:57:47

community? Just be

chelle gentemann 2:57:52

so just to note that if they're not in our slides, it's not because we're not outreaching with them or talking with them. It's just an oversight on our part in most of these cases. We were just participating in NGO Fair last week. And, of course, we're closely connected to the Research Data Alliance. And if we are overlooking things, please, you know, raise issues on our GitHub, let us know that you think we're not connecting with somebody that we should be connecting with, raise discussions and reach out to us.

Cynthia Hall 2:58:30

And ask them if you have contacts and a lot of these places that we should be reaching. We would love to have those on to how have you helped make a connection between us? And them? Yeah.

chelle gentemann 2:58:40

And also to say that a little just to give a little caveat

2:58:47

is the Bella

chelle gentemann 2:58:48

Cindy, Yvonne and I are tops right now. We would love to be everywhere talking to everyone. But I think what was it was like 65 presentations and it we've we've been doing our best and we will continue to

Yvonne Ivey 2:59:07

do so. But we're also trying to prioritize work life balance and mental health as we move into a year where I think I counted, I'll be gone from home for 75 days.

2:59:19

So yeah,

chelle gentemann 2:59:20

so we have a project office coming on that is going to help a lot with this. So we are getting about six more people. We also are building our networks of Tufts champions. And we're starting to really build quickly.

2:59:36

And it's, and initially

chelle gentemann 2:59:37

our focus is a little bit more on the US just because we had to choose we can't do it all. So the first year we decided we are a little bit more focused on the US we are doing some international meetings, and then the next year is to continue building and growing.

Malvika Sharan 2:59:56

Malvika here except for the World Data Systems. rest of the folks who are leading or engaging with the project are in open core SMEs. So you have you from your data. You have Esther and Sarah. Yeah. So all of them are there. And I think I mean, just to bring it up that although you can mention everybody's community, I see that you are engaging with them.

chelle gentemann 3:00:18

Yeah. And you, Vaughn and I were just and I think this is later is we're actually going to ask you to highlight all of your communities in this discussion. Yeah.

Yvonne Ivey 3:00:26

Because we, we, it's, I learned there meet these in California, which is not a thing of a spread word, these follow you when you're eating the Metis, which I learned something new today. We were sitting talking about the morning, and I realized that we were referencing nonprofits and organizations that many people don't know what they are, you know, turning away carpentries to ITC, we should probably define them for folks. So that they're aware of the the work that folks are doing, but also all the other ones that are who are in the room like NumPy and Creative Commons, like we would like for you all to actually share, kind of provide perspective on what your organization's are doing.

isabella martinez 3:01:16

We have a question in the chat, which is a great comment for us, which is do you have a semi could you remove the closed captions, which despite my best efforts? Oh, we continue to chat right in the mouth. Thank you. Yeah. So Susan said, Do you have a stakeholder map that shows who is engaged where and doing what with so many elements that can be hard to identify gaps and needs when you aren't sure what activities are covered or engaging with various groups? Is there a place to see this?

chelle gentemann 3:01:49

I want to Okay, Cindy?

3:01:54

Thank you for your question. We are working on it. I think

brooks hanson 3:02:02

I just wanted to comment that I've had a few meetings with Benoit Perry

3:02:07

Castle, David Castle

Jim Colliander 3:02:09

is a chair of one of the data groups at the World Data System about tops. So I just wanted people to know that the world data systems leadership is very much aware of tops. They're based at the University of Victoria in Canada, which I think gives opportunities for some of us connected to Canada to do things up there as well.

3:02:30

Thank you. We are engaged.

Fernando Perez 3:02:39

I just had an eye for an enterprise again from Berkeley, I just had an A idea of. So back to back to my point about connecting with countries beyond the US. But understanding the constraint, the legal constraint that the House operates on how we can like hack the system a little bit in a good way. And so, for example, two weeks ago, I had an event with some of your NASA colleagues participated, hosted at UC Berkeley, for the launching of a new center of good writing called data science for the environment. This is philanthropic Lee funded. So I do have a lot of freedom on how I use those funds

in that event. And one of the things I did was invited some Colombian scientists to come and participate in this and interesting potential avenues for collaboration around climate modeling. And we're that event for Colombian scientist, any connection, which need not be monetary, right, with NASA in a scientific capacity will be valuable, right, it will be important it will. So to the extent that you could imagine, and you can engineer ways in which NASA could partner with those of us who might have ways of using resources using using funds to connect, for example, to scientists in Latin America, which is kind of what I'm doing in this space. It doesn't need to be that you've ever sent \$1 of NASA con to an account in Colombia, which may be legally complicated. But there's other there's other assets that NASA has, that can be a value. And maybe some of us can find those mechanisms to make that engagement in even under umbrellas that we're already doing anyway. And believe me, the simple seal for scientists in Colombia of having a partnership with a NASA program will be valuable, professionally motivating and open doors. So just an idea. I mean, I don't have anything specific that we could do, but something to think about while respecting the constraints you operate on.

chelle gentemann 3:04:33

One thing that we have been doing is reaching out to some of our subject matter experts who are all around the world. And when we've been offered opportunities for keynotes, actually asking them to go and not only represent tops, but also represent their groups and their communities so that we it's sort of a win win for each of us. And we've just started doing that with some of the subject matter Experts who contributed to open floor and we're hoping to do a lot more of that in the future. And that's one way so that they get that connection to NASA. And they also get to elevate, you know, their voices as well. And if there's other ideas like, but it seems like we're like, oh, we're giving them a keynote, it's like, that's not what I need, right. But like, there's other ways and opportunities that you can think of that we can help to elevate people globally. Like, we'd love to hear more about that.

Fernando Perez 3:05:28

Maybe drafting a bit of a oh, sorry, just to finish. Like, it might be worth thinking. And this is better done off of specific, like inductively by having one or two examples, but like thinking of drafting what could like an asset tops, little MOU look like with a researcher in Latin America with a researcher or like something that would be palatable to NASA. But that could be official for them. That could have a lot of value at zero, like social and scientific value without involving any transfer of funds.

chelle gentemann 3:05:59

And we get requests like that Fernando, and I haven't quite like I've seen requests like this come in. And I don't think that we had quite figured out what to do with them. And this actually like is usually resonating with me,

3:06:13

I think, sorry, there's a shark element. That one thing that

Malvika Sharan 3:06:23

we were, I could suggest from how we are doing that is, sir, it's Malpica. And I work with the Turing waiver, we do lots of community building, and we get a lot of our community members to deliver trainings and workshops. They do keynotes and talks, we, we build a set of promotional materials, and

we get people to adopt that in their own languages in their own projects. We actively get more than one person to talk together, because, technically speaking, and research generally one speaker speaks, but I've learned from an elder WonderWorld, who once did a keynote where she got 10 of her community members come in and give five minutes talk about their own work. And that was just mind blowing. And I think that's very much in the spirit of open science. How can we shared the spaces with people, rather than one person? Can we get to people? If I remember what I was going to say, oh, yeah, there's another one debate. Right? Like, how can how can we actually have a balanced discussion? Because sometimes people don't enter open science space, assuming they're, oh, I have apprehension if I go, and people won't hear me because they just want us to learn about Open Science. How can we create those forums for people to actually share their concerns, fears? It could be combined with locks, can we publish people's profile their, you know, celebrating challenges and problems rather than problematizing them? And also, like you have so many centers of nurses. So maybe there could be a central profiling for what open work is already going on in there. So giving kudos kudos to people who are doing the work.

3:08:08

We have five minutes left for this discussion.

Jordan Adams 3:08:10

Do we have a question in there? Yeah, Jordan Adams planetary data system. I just one thought that came to my head was COSPAR is an international scientific conference that's actually blessed by the United Nations. It's actually how, for planetary, we have an international planetary Data Alliance that's was actually out of COSPAR. And it's kind of how we're actually at PDS for NASA able to provide some support for the actual group that collaborates. So it's not quite going to be adding funding, but it allows ways for NASA to support international efforts without having all of the paperwork necessary to actually do any kind of collaboration. So we had to leave in a lease payment kicked off. So maybe there's keynotes or something there that would really get at an international level across all the sciences. Right. That's just this. I forget what it stands for on this level, but committee on

chelle gentemann 3:09:05

luckily, I sat on a committee with lead. So I will reach out to him that thank you. That's a great idea.

brooks hanson 3:09:15

I want to since Jim Cole Leander, I wanted to follow up on Fernando suggestion about mo use. So I used to serve as an institute director. And there were many opportunities to sign mo use with other Institute's or other universities elsewhere. And most of these are like a little announced double. And then there's this document, and no, nothing really happens thereafter. So that's nice. But there's a big exception for the institute that I ran, and that was our partnership with the CNRS of France. So CNRS has a very different view about international partnerships than the United States or Canada has. They actually invest significant money outside of France, because they want to be strongly connected with the researcher. that are going on out there. And they have a network of 80 different what are called IRS international research laboratories across different disciplines. I suspect that the NASA tops leadership could connect with leadership at CNRS, and discuss ways to connect with their international research laboratory network. And if you made an MOU with CNS at the scale, you're gonna connect with at labs

all across the globe, and you'll be able to rely upon the CNRS network, to engage. I don't think there's any money involved necessarily in that exchange. But I think there's enough of a synergy and it's such a big network across, you know, colonial colonized Africa by the French, and far west of the Far East and elsewhere. They're just really awesome in building international partnerships. And so I suggest you explore CNRS as a possible partner,

Yvonne Ivey 3:10:50

All I know about MOU so far, is what Kevin has told me, which is, there's take a long time. And there's lawyers involved? Definitely know that. That we have time we have five years. And it seems like if we're going to do it, that would be that that might be an investment worth making.

Kevin Murphy 3:11:56

So maybe, hey, there's KevinMurphy, NASA. I know that we keep on saying that, you know, like tops is certainly a five year investment that we're making, right? NASA's commitment to open science, however, is not going to stop with tops. So I think that that's important to say as well. We, you know, really want to get guidance on on things like partnerships where, you know, the initial investments we make, can be kind of diffused throughout the groups. And yeah, just become science on open science anymore. As much as possible. But we will continue to support both through our policies and our investments and our incentives, open science practices, well beyond the five year timeline, timeline, right. So all of the suggestions for groups that we can work with, to do more work is better. Because you know, like, at the end of the day, the way that I think that we should structure our programs, is to not take the money and get more and more people at NASA to go tell everybody else what they should be doing. But it's to take the money that we have invested in the community grants or cooperative agreements are other mechanisms that they can go out and do that work. Right. So So part of it is what can we do internally to kind of jumpstart it. And that's really what Topps is meant to do. But the longer term plan is to make sure that the community gets our funding to do that, through you know, partnerships through with with, you know, the different professional organizations or Institute's or whomever, right so you guys can help us find those critical relationships. I think that that that will be super helpful because they're there for people. And I'm sure it'll change the world but a couple more will help

isabella martinez 3:14:02

on that very scary note of confidence from Kevin. I think transition.

chelle gentemann 3:14:09

Are we supposed to do that Yoga Retreat in Maui? Me?

3:20:23

We really want to hear from our panelists, as Ivana shall were saying earlier about what all of you are working on the communities that you represent, and the ways that you think we can work together. This is also conversations that I think we've begun to have. So I would love it, maybe if we began on this Because nobody has already explained how we can work together. And actually, maybe we'll even begin with our panelists who are virtual, and take that back and then move into the people in the room on now that we've kind of had three quarters of a day talking about where we're moving forward, the

way we've integrated your feedback from last time into our plans, and how to improve upon that feedback moving forward, is the ways that you particularly see how the communities you're a part of could be could help us out with our mission. Especially as we keep saying the core team gathers more right now it is growing, I want to do a shout out to Sam, Ryan eata and Jerrica. Were also part of our core team and have all been on online today. But we still need help. That's still the eight people so Alright, that's enough for me.

3:21:41

And would you like to start?

3:21:42

We'll do so here. Okay. That'd be like midnight there. Oh, yeah, that's true. Do you want to start? Can you hear?

Pen-Yuan Hsing 3:22:12

i Sorry, I dropped out for for a little bit. I'm a little bit behind. Can't keep him up again. Which page we're on right now. Yeah, sorry.

isabella martinez 3:22:22

No, that's totally okay. We ended our break very promptly.

3:22:26

We were asking

isabella martinez 3:22:29

chelle wants you to play the piano, but I'm not gonna put you on the spot. That's what you were asking about. The one wanted to begin with you if you're comfortable talking about, like,

Monica Granados 3:22:48

what are you up to right now?

isabella martinez 3:22:49

And based on the discussions we've had so far today? How do you think we could work with the communities you're a part of in order to do any of the things that we've talked about your of open science? What happens after so on so forth?

Pen-Yuan Hsing 3:23:03

Um, okay, thank you, I can think of a few things that I can go over as quickly as possible. Oh, actually, now that I think about it, maybe on another one. But anyway, the first one is that, you know, obviously, I've been doing a lot of open science advocacy in different forms over many years. And one thing I'm still doing is that I, you know, almost regularly these days, get invited to give talks and lecture lectures at different institutions and universities have kind of been doing it on my own, this whole time. For example, I'm going to be giving a lecture at a university, University virtually next year in February, on open science and open educational resources and all that stuff. So going forward, I would love to have

some sort of way to coordinate with you, you know, on the different kinds of outreach and engagement and education that we're doing, maybe, you know, so we can build up a map of some of the different communities were reaching out to this kind of stuff. So maybe some sort of coordination with logistics. Number two, is that I am also somewhat involved on the UNESCO open science recommendations side of things. I know you're pretty involved in that as well. So it might be helpful to not only coordinate with that, but also who was going to say, Oh, yes, one part of that, that we've identified as a gap is for the people contributing to the UNESCO process there. The vast majority of them are still working on you know, the open access open data open source software. side of things. And I think something that they're really missing is the kind of engagement with wider society side. A lot of people from outside of traditional scientific institutions who are doing, you know, important research in science are not really represented in that, however, from what they're for today, and also the work that I've seen that you did over the past months, you know, you worked with, for example, this is in Science Association. Or I saw one of the badges, one of the logos, you put up on one of the slides, you've talked to public lab, I believe, I think that's fantastic. And I'm wondering, if you're contributing to that side of things on the UNESCO effort as well, I'm working with them on that, and I in them are really looking for that. So I wonder if there's some way, you know, we can work together on this front, just, you know, a big part of that is also incorporating and valuing indigenous knowledge. So that's a particularly interesting part. And I think, very, very important. The other thing is that I briefly mentioned this before, a long term thing I've been working on is worth a group called the gathering for open science, right? Where we're actually having a big conference, at the end of this month, it's going to be in Panama, because we always make a point of holding these conferences, outside of the Global North. And, and, and again, you know, I'm by I'm in a leadership position in that group. So I'll be very happy to coordinate will work with any of you here today, to see whether we can find some sort of synergy there. Because I really find the hardware side of things still be very lacking in open science discourse. So that's something I love to explore. And, lastly, I just go back to my point earlier about arts and humanities involvement in open science. And I, I, this is the probably the least specific thing that I'm talking about right now. But I also look forward to doing some stuff from there as well, in particular, on the nature of science, the philosophy, of science, of why open science is good science, kinds of discussions, I think those fundamental reflections are important. Oh, and lastly, very quick, quick thing about something I'm working on through the next year is that I am based at the University of Bristol in the UK. And I am working with people from the UK reproducibility network on a new publishing platform called octopus. It's www.octopus.ac. And it is focused on scientific publishing, where you break down publishing into its component parts, right? So instead of publishing a big paper, you can publish, you know, your research idea as a sizable publication with a DOI, you can publish your methodology as individual paper, you can publish a data paper, and that kind of stuff is breaking down scientific publishing into small pieces. And on top of that, is trying to create a layer where you can create a web have these different pieces building on each other, right. So let's say someone publishes a research idea. People might build on that, and link to them on the octopus platform, publish different methodologies, for them to look into that idea, and that kind of stuff. So it can create a world of different interactions, which leads me to my point from earlier today, I think it'd be fantastic to develop some way to measure and recognize not only the creation of open science outputs, but how people are reusing and re mixing that material into new scientific discoveries. So this kind of like an overview of the many things I'm working on. I don't know if this answers your question adequately, but I didn't want to ramble on for too long. So maybe I'll leave it at that for now. Thank you.

Yvonne Ivey 3:29:34

Thank you. And there's there's no right answer. Again, we really wanted to give folks an opportunity to kind of share the work that they're doing, because we were throwing out organizations and we realized that maybe we're not being inclusive for the folks who are new in their journey. So next on the call is Brian still

Cynthia Hall 3:29:54

I think Brian in teaching or had to leave maybe look Oh

chelle gentemann 3:30:00

to Monica. And then maybe back online if we find another online panel. Yeah.

3:30:05

And everyone has approximately seven minutes. Because I want us to make sure we get to everyone. Sorry. No, thank you. We're good. You are within time. I just hadn't said that.

Pen-Yuan Hsing 3:30:17

Thank you. I'm glad you're on time. Yeah. Oh, sorry. One quick thing if that's okay. Since since since since you know, it good to be here. So, as part of developing the octopus platform, I just I just mentioned, I am looking for some people to interview on establishing researchers current understanding of research culture, and what they perceive the problems are with division of labor, giving attribution and credit and publishing in your field. Right. So just a quick, quick ad, if anyone's interested in being interviewed or know of people who would have something important to say on this topic, please let me know I will love to talk to you with them. Thank you. Hi, everyone.

Monica Granados 3:31:15

I'm Monica grace. Again, I work at Creative Commons. I'm the open climate campaign manager. And I also am on the leadership team of free review. But I'll start talking about Creative Commons first. So Creative Commons, sort of the tagline here is we're a nonprofit organizations that helps overcome legal obstacles to the sharing of knowledge, and creativity to address the world's most pressing problems. So if you I've ever used the CC by license, or CC zero, which is what you know, we advocate to use data on, you have used the infrastructure that Creative Commons has as created. Really, what we're trying to do is simplify some of the complex legal language and obstacles to make it easier for folks to share data and information. I specifically work on a project called the Open climate campaign. It's a four year project to make the open sharing of research in biodiversity and climate science, the norm, so sort of what Topps is doing, but now, specifically for climate change in biodiversity research, because we recognize that to solve the world's greatest problems, and knowledge about them needs to be open. And so we very similar, I have a four year project. And so I think there's a lot of places where we can work together, and I've started made over. The first is that, you know, for some of the open core work that you've done, I think we had a conference, I've had a conversation with my colleague, table green, and you shall to talk about potentially doing some training on CC licenses, I think it's helpful to know especially if you're sending your data out into you know, the public as well as your your papers to understand what a what a, how a license can enable sharing while still making it over your work. So

having a good and we have, like, you know, things that you could take off the shelf and implement into your program or, you know, we could do some kind of collaborative work so that we come in and train, you know, a cohort of your, of your practitioners. You also could come and do a podcast, we have a cc podcast. And then in return, I'd love to write one of the blog posts that came up. Yes, count, I said, I will I or cable or both of us will write and then amplify it through the CC network, which is also like I think has like 300,000 Twitter followers, for example. And then, of course, I think we really need to do the joint pre conference event. I think that's like kind of a no brainer. We've got funding for that, to go to this event, and that way, you know, we're not doing it by ourselves and like a joint NASA Creative Commons thing would be would be awesome. Yeah. And then lastly, yeah, I work also on pre review. It's a platform that uses preprints to help people make the review of of like, peer reviewed papers more open and transparent and equitable. So we train people on how to do peer review. We have a platform to help doing to do peer review and we also do these cool things called Live preprint journal clubs, where we do like virtual reviews of a preprint with like, different people all across the world. And so I've my colleagues have already been they're part of the open core curriculum and already so I think we're pretty plugged in there already.

Logan Kilpatrick 3:34:52

Okay, well that you were we gonna check online for anything Was it no one else? No, no? Cool. How's it going everyone, my name is Logan Kilpatrick, I'm on the board of directors that focus for folks who don't know what num focus is. It's a nonprofit 501 C three that provides the legal and financial infrastructure for open source projects to basically accept money and do all the types of things that you would want to do if you're an open source project, and centralizes, all that infrastructure under the non focus umbrella so that our 50 Plus projects don't have to go out and make their own entities and manage all the taxes and all that situation. So concentrating all that, as well as providing a bunch of educational programs like al data and other conferences, for the open source ecosystem. I think, and I know, Schultz had a bunch of these conversations with Leo, who's the executive director, and I'm focused already at the summit the last couple of weeks. But there's so there's so many opportunities for us to, for us to work together. I think we started a year and a half, two years ago, something like that putting together the non focus Academy was really sort of similar ideas to the open core, which is we need to get this curriculum, whether it's focused around scientific tools, or just sort of the broad principles of open science into the hands of and in front of the eyes of developers and users of tools and things like that. So I think going back to Jim's idea about like, being able to deploy the curriculum in different places, I think the num focus Academy could be a great place to do. So. We also spent a lot of money building that infrastructure. So I don't know. And it's not really utilized well, at the present moment. So I don't know if there's actually, Jim, to your point about deploying things, I don't know if we can reuse some of that and make it so that we don't have to spend money building new things. That's something that we can definitely explore. And I think there's other people Lorraine, who was one of the former board members who was at some of these meetings before, I think she's she's more hands on and involved in that and can can touch on it. We also have the academic Consortium, which is a new nonprofit initiative, which is partnerships between them focus and universities, which I think could be a great thing to tap into and have those connections and make those partnerships happen. But in general, I think that probably the biggest piece is getting involved with tops curriculum at non focus events, the PI Data events that happen all over the world, Julia Khan, Sai pi, all those events, I think it's a huge distribution mechanism. And it could probably double the impact that you are proposing the

slide that had like 100,000 attendees or something like that, I think there's a huge opportunity to make it a lot more than that, if we had the right partnerships in place.

chelle gentemann 3:37:43

Do you think the PI Data community would be interested in open science curriculum?

3:37:50

Yeah, because I think and turnout and I were talking about this, or I might have mentioned that before, but I think there's there's so many, there's so much crossover, like the people who are involved in the Python ecosystem that are attending those events are generally people who are doing open science, there are users of these open source tools, who are researchers or practitioners, and I think it's 100% would be would be interested in that curriculum. So I think it would be a huge opportunity to make that happen. Yeah. And I also think just one other quick note, which was around, I also do stuff a bunch of stuff from the Giulia programming language. So I think, I don't know I'm I'm unfamiliar, and I haven't seen this specific open core curriculum yet. But I think ensuring that not just for the sake of my own vested interest in the success of Giulia, but just languages in general, whether it's our Python, etc, etc, making sure that the curriculum is like, built in a way that it can be agnostic to those languages and other things can tie in and, again, going back to Jim's idea of sort of letting people build on top of it, having sort of places where you can say, oh, you're a Python user, you know, add in your stuff here, your whatever user,

ch 3:39:00

I think our next panelist is, okay. Yeah.

SherAaron Hurt 3:39:12

Hey, everyone, I am sure Aaron, I am with the carpentries, Director of workshops, and some of the things that we're working on here. So currently, we are actually working on a we have funding from the Alfred P Sloan Foundation, to build an Equity Council to increase the amount or to increase our instructors and to put workshops in front of people that look more people of color. And so that is a huge event, while the grant ends this year. That's just you know, as we've been talking about, yes, we're getting the funding. But that also means that once we're done, we want to expand that outside of the United States, but really looking at, you know, making sure that when we do one of our initiatives, and one of our goals is to be able to put our resources workshops and instructors in front of some of the underrepresented communities. But the thing is, when we get in those communities, we don't have instructors that look like them. So we want to make sure that we are being intentional about putting instructors that look like them in front of them. We are also a recipient of the A d i, CBI grant, which I think carries we saw Kerry last week, our executive director. And so with that, we are we've created created a toolkit of ideas, which I think will be great to share in that. It is it's a it's a toolkit that allows us to say whenever you're getting ready to go in any workshop or any event, these are the types of things that you need to consider to make sure that your workshop your event is accessible for all and that isn't that again, not just for a workshop, but for any event that you're thinking about. So thinking about your audience, before you even step foot in front of that audience, you've thought about all the things right. Other things that we do ongoing things that we do, we have our study groups, which is something that our curriculum team leads for people that are interested in developing their own lesson. So we've talked

about, you know, people get involved in open science, well, what are the different avenues or facets, maybe I want to help develop curriculum, we do have a program in place for that in which people can come and get involved with. In addition to that, we have what's called our incubator lessons. So while we have our carpentry standard core lessons, those are the ones that are tried and true, we do have opportunities for people who have developed, who have developed lesson plans, or maybe they're developing and they want feedback, people can go out and test them for them, so that they can become carpenters lessons, it just to get that feedback. So that's another opportunity. And then when we talk about community, so we have a community, our director of community, we realized that we want to make sure that we have the resources and things that needs to be done. The carpentry is while we are a global institution, we're still relatively a small team. We're a team of 1616 people, and very US centric, there's maybe five of us that are in the US, I'm sorry, that are outside of the US. And with that our but our community is global. And so with that we want to we have a community development program that community our community development team is creating with that it is really setting each community up for success, noting that each community is different, the way we run things in Chicago may look different in LA, right. So when you take that outside of the US what that looks like outside of the US could be totally different. So we're developing a program so that we have community coordinators, who are able to really lead the charge of starting the carpenters community in the area. So for us, it would be you know, that opportunities, I would say, to be able to show how we are going to take open science outside of the US but make sure that it fits the language or the environment of wherever we're going. Um, and then lastly, we do have our community discussions similar to what we do, you know, here in the Open Science and an idea that I thought about was we generally do thing community discussion. So it very could, it could be possible that one of the month we say hey, let's do a NASA tops coming into discussion for the carpentries community that we can collaborate and say this is we want to bring, you know, we want you to come to the carpentries and just talk about talk about what's happened and how we can get in and out. And we can do one two, however, we really want to do that. Hi, everyone,

Malvika Sharan 3:43:50

I'm Malika Sharon, I'm based in London and very jet lagged. I co lead two projects, which are community led community oriented. The first one is the cheering weights, community led handbook on data science and research. We focus so our moonshot goal is to make reproducibility too easy enough to do. No problem we can obviously do. But the project is absolutely open source open research. And we involve community in building best practices that they need. So far, we have over 350 contributors. We've built over 250 chapters across project design, communication, collaboration, and research, reproducibility tools and practices, as well as ethical research. Make fun of the carpentries and share. One thing that I really love from the carpentries, which I took into my project is community handbook. It's about really making sure that we make implicit knowledge explicit by defining every single thing we do. So anybody can fork that committee handbook and apply that in their own in their own context. We work very domain agnostic. But we are also working very specifically with people who are applying these practices of their own domains like health research in energy systems in industry, and academia, and more, much more. So I'm gonna plug something which I'm really proud of two days ago, I received half a million fund from our organization to build something called practitioner hub. And the reason is that we saw that there were a lot of organizations who were very interested in were using the during way in their own context, we just didn't have the capacity to work with them, and help them apply, as

well as help them build some case studies, something that you will, we're talking about how can we make our materials more relatable for domains. So that's something that we are going to work on in the next phase. Starting next month, some of our community members are localizing our resources, our materials are written by people across global north and the south. And we also recognize that we still write a lot of things from western point of view. So our community leaders come from Saudi Arabia, but MARSOC, we have people coming from Latin America who are translating it in Spanish, we have a group that has just tried to translate in Turkish partial translation has been done in French and Chinese as well. And the localization work is not just about translate this thing, but really localize and contextualize it into your own context, change the example right personal story that is, that is reflecting your own point of view. And this community, the sub communities is also helping the sector power governance more, more structured way, one of the things that I worked early on in the project was around acknowledgement process and policy. So we really, really did focus on championing people's contribution, how can they own the project, not just contribute to the project? How can they just take it what is there and be recognized for it. So we have developed a huge policy, one of the one of the things that we do is to create a dedicated page for people to write about what they have done, what they're proud of what they want to take forward. So somewhat helping them build an informal skill set that they can take in their CV. So you know, we don't need to define what incentive looks like for them, they write what is meaningful for them. reusing materials are, of course, thanks to CC by everybody is, you know, people should really really use it very much in Logan and Monica, Monica's point that, you know, we build this thing together with lots of people, we really want others to really look at it and reuse it and challenge it and change it. Data, the case study development we already talked about, we are working with another project to build an infrastructure where people can write case studies which they can query. So anybody can pull it into their own training material or any context that they're interested in. There's one project that is a part of sort of, during this part, being supported by the Alan Turing Institute, it's the National Center for data science. And we come across, I have come across a lot of challenges around you know, institutional change. And what we initially focused on, which I really, really admire about the community is not really working only internally, but working externally to build evidence and impact of our work and show our organization, how meaningful and important this is. And now we're working inward. So I think you're doing like you're doing in the same space. But we work externally a lot more. And now we're focusing inward to build this practitioner help and work with people internally. And in the institute, there's a program called AI for Science and Government that once my position and one of the work that they did was in environmental sustainability, and I'm trying to write a report from them because the program is ending, and one of their future builders will fill in environment. And although I'm not researching environmental research, I'm really happy to put folks who are going to hold up who are building this program in touch because they're doing some really incredible work they're working with British Arctic survey they're working with, with communities in Africa in mapping how climate change can be controlled. Through community engagement. There are many projects, but these two are my favorite. Another one is seals from space. They are tracking seals from space, using computer vision, and those are all open source. The last project that I'll talk about is open like science. It's a project that I lead co lead with my colleague, so UD, who's open core lead one of the leads, Amy sang and Bernice Batou. We do a 16 week long training and mentoring program where people bring their project and they're paired with a mentor, who can help contextualize open science in their own project. So these are, of course open to anybody and we're very, very happy to work with you to get some now So researchers bringing their project into that. But we are also developing intense week. So rather than

doing 16 week, we can also do one week training. I feel that 16 weeks a lot more important than one week because it does do this cultural change. And we're doing some research as well. Meta research on how, how mentoring is transformative. So not just assessing at the end of the program, but assessing six months later, and one year later, have they taken this practice in different projects, just because these evidences are not there, we need to build those evidences. And one of the strength of the community is really diversity. People come from all around the world. And I don't think our community would be the same if we weren't witnessing that diversity. So one thing that I would say, yes, open science, you're being funded by government in the US. But when you say open, it's open for everybody. And we need to take that responsibility to widen that boundary and inspire people to worry about that to worry about is my work going outside the US as well and choose for themselves if they want to be involved.

brooks hanson 3:51:06

Okay, so, this is Jim Caliendo, and I'll tell you a little bit about some of the work that to ITC has been up to. So to itu C stands for the International interactive computing collaboration. It's a relatively new organization that I was very pleased to co found with community panelist, Fernando and a collection of other superstars that I'm really happy to be able to collaborate with now. So we provide managed Jupiter hub service that delivers more than Jupyter Notebooks. So it's kind of a batteries included Jupiter hub system that can be adapted to a variety of community needs. With a shared responsibility model so that discipline specific experts can customize and tailor the way the infrastructure is used by those communities. We run infrastructure in a pilot right now with cloud bank, and UC Berkeley, that is delivering this infrastructure for emerging data science programs at collection of emphasize and the California State system. We run an infrastructure for large universities like the University of Toronto, we support a collection of research communities, we run the infrastructure for Pan Geo, and pan geo cousins leap and empty lines that are affiliated with Columbia and New York University. We've launched a hub that it serves the Alabama Water Institute that's trying to get data insights into the National Water model that does flood preparedness. And we've also recently been the recipient or the subcontracted recipient of a Twisk award on the NASA cryo sphere activity. And Fernando may say more about that in a minute. So at UCSF values led organization with transformational goals, we enable the use of commercial cloud in a vendor agnostic way. So our strategy allows research communities for education communities, to use Google Cloud. And if for some reason, they need to move off of Google, they should seamlessly be able to move to Azure, or move to AWS. And in this way, we make commercial cloud into a utility that is independent of their login. So our strategy avoids a vendor lock in and makes it a kind of an agnostic service. To make this happen. It's mobilized in this right to replicate that Fernando referenced, which I think is a very subtle invention by my colleague, UV panda. So we have infrastructure that can deliver proprietary software, but the infrastructure is open, and based on open science. So this is a new business continuity promise, if one of our customers decides that they no longer want to use to ITC as the manager of the service, they can take the playbook for running the infrastructure because it's public and run it themselves. From A to A to C makes a lot of revenue point of view, this looks like we're shooting ourselves in the foot. But it's actually advancing our mission. Because through this approach, if someone does leave our management, it means that the expertise in DevOps and Site Reliability Engineering that we initially provided, is now provided by someone else. And so we've diversified the community of expertise that runs these kinds of platforms. And in so doing, we've improved the community for managing science and data intensive research. The last thing that I

want to comment on which I think speaks to some of the return on investment that the Open Science Initiative at NASA is going to achieve is that through my perspective at ITC, I'm observing new models for the scientific enterprise starting to take root. So collaborators working together with common tools adjacent to large data is a new way to engage in scientific activity. And this enables research products like a notebook to be shared quickly with others who can then interact with the common tool chain and the common data and learn fast. So instead of waiting for knowledge to do fuse through the preprint process through the review process through the publication process through someone reading the article and then finally telling a decision maker there's this new idea that's going to help save the planet we are I think making knowledge connect

Jim Colliander 00:00

only telling a decision maker, there's this new idea that's going to help save the planet. We are, I think making knowledge connect instead of diffuse. And in this way, there is a shortening of the time interval between research impacts on operations. And I'm seeing that in this Alabama Water Institute example and emerging discussions in the heliophysics community. So as I understand the National Water model situation that the Alabama Water Institute is developing, the National Water model is a data product created by NOAA. And it provides data that generates insights into whether or not a community is at risk of flood. But states are responsible for mobilizing flood response. So states wait for reports from NOAA scientists that there's a risk. But if instead, we had the people that mobilize the state's action, interacting with the data live, and looking at the reports live, they may be able to customize and combine the federal data with their proprietary or their state information and make faster operational decisions rather than waiting on the federal government. And I think this is going to change across all disciplines of science, where we can all communicate our ideas faster, and make our work composable. What does that mean for the whole enterprise? Thank you don't.

Fernando Perez 01:24

Like shell, so I'm trying to enterprise kind of were a few different hats in this space. My official one is that impacted UC Berkeley, and scientists at Lawrence Berkeley National Lab. And in there, I am currently kind of working on a few different fronts. One, which I briefly mentioned, that I think is relevant to this space is a new film publicly funded center called data science for the environment that tries to build impact driven solutions for for environmental conservation and climate change. That that are, that needs to be based in open opening principles of both full development and community engagement. And so the focus here is on building building things that will be put in the hands of stakeholders and built with stakeholders to advance environmental conservation of Shell kindly provided contact one of our colleagues at NASA and Dr. Mo Cherington, who joined us two weeks ago, in this event, he's building capacity in Africa and was was wonderful, wonderful participant. At this event. We started a new initiative at Berkeley also with separate philanthropic funding for bitmap, which is one material science for the development of new materials around carbon capture, hydrogen capture, etc, are classes of materials called metal metal organic frameworks, led by a physical chemist at UC Berkeley. But with a strong emphasis on building open open infrastructure for expert others, other scientists all over the world to be able to access kind of cutting edge materials to solve environmental problems in their own communities. On now wearing my teacher hat at UC Berkeley, I teach a couple of courses that are kind of in the space. I teach the upper division course of our data science major called data 100 principles and techniques of data science. And I also teach a course called collaborative and

reproducible research. And on both of those courses, Shell has been kindly a guest lecturer and actually scheduled to guest lecture two weeks from now at my class. And in the collaborative and reproducible Data Science course, we actually had our students work on reproducing shells last MATLAB based kind of non open source paper before she kind of became a card carrying member of the NGO community. And it was an absolutely fantastic experiment that maybe shell can tell you a little bit about over dinner. And that infrastructure for education is built at Berkeley around public, cloud deployed Jupiter hubs. Berkeley has a big, big operation, where we run Jupiter hubs for education. To give you an idea, my dad on her class has about 1200 students, the lower division of that class has 1800 students, we deploy about 15 different hubs in the cloud that serve the needs of the entire campus. It was the catastrophic success to pick a term from Tracy to from the formula, the carpentries that led us to join forces with Jim and others in founding to wait to see as an organization that could replicate these models have hosted hubs for large educational communities, at other institutions in a way that one community University is not really well suited for serving that but if anyone is interested in kind of just these kinds of things at large scale, we we do that and I should be holding office hours about an hour ago but I'm here instead. Moving on to my Jupiter work i The project that became Jupiter was my PhD procrastination project back in grad school. And these days, obviously I'm not writing code for Jupiter But one aspect that perhaps maybe useful for these conversations is all the work we've been doing around governance of Jupiter. Moving Jupiter from a project that was kind of a one off individual endeavor to something that could accept funding that could manage resources that could see themes led to the foundation of non focus. I was a co founder of nonprofits with others back in 2012. And establishing models for Fiscal Sponsorship for formalize governance, these kinds of things in open source community is something that we've been doing in Jupiter and related projects for a number of years to try to basically balance this idea of how do you get a how do you organize the structure or random community of people on the internet to manage a project that can seek funding in a structured way that for where people can build careers and so on and so forth. I'm happy to talk about that today to see which is an organization that I co founded with Jim and other colleagues. Besides what Jim said, I guess the one point I should flag on expand a little bit on this idea of the cranial hub. It was an idea that together with cryosphere scientists called Tasha snow that also collaborates with Shell, Jim and I, we kind of brainstormed on, on what I think is kind of an interesting little community hack, which was, how can we build this kind of infrastructure for a community without claiming that communities ground right without claiming ownership of that community's ground. And the idea of which then thanks to Tasha leadership turned into a grant that talks is now funding was, Don't claim the ground for the community, partner with organizers of specific workshops that have legitimacy already in that scientific space to offer a persistent hob that can go from workshop one in January to workshop to inmate workshop three in December, we're now those those workshops are going to happen anyway. But now there's a persistent digital watering hole where the data and the computing can come together and people can aggregate and congregate around that. And instead of claiming bare ground, you are offering what we hope will become a nucleation center for communities to aggregate around that the cryosphere one is now funded and it's being led by cash now is being stood up as we speak, the lset to science mission team will participate in it in addition to a few workshops, and if that's the model that annual you're interested in learning about Jim and I are happy to talk to you about it. And I'm also connected via your notebooks, notebooks now project will command you per hand, but I suppose may say more about that.

chelle gentemann 07:22

Thank you. Thanks. This was so useful. I'm so glad we did. Thank you everyone for sharing all the stuff that you're doing.

Yvonne Ivey 07:36

An incredible group of panelists, seats we knew y'all

Cynthia Hall 07:40

were rock stars, but like I have like three pages of notes.

isabella martinez 07:46

So we're actually going to change up the agenda a tiny bit. The current agenda shows that we're going to take an hour to do the collaborative GitHub activity I mentioned earlier, take another break, and then moved into the final like formal discussion for today, we were chatting, and we actually think it's better to do the formal discussion. Now. That way, if folks who've been sticking with us online, want to kind of bed and continue to get up on their own time, they can do so. So we'll do the friend discussion, I will explain the GitHub activity, we will move into a break. And then we'll spend the rest of the time having more informal discussions. And we're going to turn off the recording at that point. All right. So during that time, we can also figure out who's driving and who's Uber. All right. So without further ado, I'm actually going to skip that if want to try to share with you. All right. So the discussion prompt is on slide 78. And it is quite straightforward, which is just, we've talked about our plans, we've gotten your feedback on our current plans. We've heard what all of you are doing and heard some excellent ideas for how we should work together. Now how to this is where we move into the thinking beyond the year of open science. How do we grow and sustain our community engagement such that it continues to grow after this one PyCon concentrated year of your open science being the theme at NASA. So big heavy topic. I don't know if Kevin wants to open the discussion here. Awesome.

Kevin Murphy 28:51

All right. I am interested in learn how we grow in sustainment though, I certainly don't think NASA can do it alone. I think that's been the message I've heard loud and clear, since this morning.

Fernando Perez 29:15

Fernando Perez from UC Berkeley, Jupiter, etc. Not to be contrarian. But the point that was made earlier, I think by Jim and a few others, resonated a lot with me about how success shouldn't necessarily be for this theme about growing a community but rather about changing all of science so that we don't need to talk so much about that. And so perhaps the question perhaps I would think about framing this question, rather than as how to grow and sustain this community. Because grow and sustain are in a sense that intention, right if it gets too big, the bigger something gets, the harder it is to sustain. Right. So Perhaps the question that I would ask is, how can it change science? To the extent that it can this effort can remain sustainable, while not necessarily being huge? Because that's another, I've been part of so many discussions about sustainability of open source communities and open source projects. And that's always a really thorny question. It's something that nonprofits struggle a lot with, right? And I think sometimes it's useful to ask, well, maybe something can be sustainable by fulfilling its mission and becoming smaller or shrinking away, or diffusing into another space and

handing off kind of its assets, ideas and impact into other other venues. And so I would encourage you to think of success. How would you different rather than how do we grow and sustain? How would you define success? Five years out? And if you can identify a certain certain milestones of success? What can you What would you imagine needing to be after that, because it doesn't mean shrinking, disappearing entirely. But maybe, rather than how to sustain something huge it is, we've had this impact. And then after that, we remain a key resource. And this particular sets of ideas that continue needing sustenance, engagement, whatever. So I would, I would invite thinking in that direction, rather than how do we make something sound as soon as simultaneously huge and sustainable, which are really two difficult things to achieve at the same time.

isabella martinez 31:23

Somebody asked in the chat, what are the goals of your one?

chelle gentemann 31:32

So, we've set our goals is five year goals. At this point, we don't have specific goals for each year, I would say that as a project for us, the end of year one looks like we have a community developed curriculum that has active contributions to it, and is growing at on its own. And that is then deployed in many different ways, or many different communities. And the year of open science is about sort of kicking off this transformation in the adoption of open science. And so at the end of the year, having a lot of those resources in place, is I think, where we want to be as a project. And a lot of that has to do with the community development curriculum. A lot of that has to do with how we're starting to engage with the roses opportunities and provide resources so that we start to have a more broader community applying for NASA's funding, and engaging with communities that we haven't engaged with before, in, in an authentic, respectful ways. And that's sort of what the end of year one for me is, is just a lot of this sort of trying to start building with the community so that we're in a place like you said, you know, we start to expand, but we, it's a, it's not just us, it's the community ownership. And we start to move towards this 30% adoption of open science within the next five years. And while we've got 20,000, for us with our community, I think we want to look at, you know, 30% of science, but we're not going to be able to do that alone.

Jim Colliander 33:28

This is Jim coriander, I'm going to make a suggestion for the NASA tops, folks that in many ways might sound offensive. But in other ways, I think there's a really interesting template to explore here. So NASA tops as a series B investment of \$40 million, you got a five year trajectory. But you did this without first achieving the goals of a seed stage investment, or the goals of a series a investment. So I recommend that you go through the process of thinking of this as a startup, and use the metaphor of all of the venture funded startups and the language. So at the end of year one, I would think that one of the goals that you want in light of the discussion earlier is that you need new channel partners. Okay, that's the offensive side of the vendor language. But if can NSF become a channel partner, can CNRS become a channel partner? And I think that if you had a board that gave you the \$40 million and wanted to hold the CEOs feet to her fire, at the end of year one, that there better be metrics that are breaking down the five year goal, so that you have a collection of milestones. I guess the last little thing that I want to suggest here is this. There's a lot of things that I don't like about this man, but there's a lot of things I like about him too. Bill Gates has this remarkable quote, which says that most humans

underestimate what they can accomplish, overestimate what they can accomplish in a year and underestimate what they can accomplish in a decade. And the power of exponentiation you know, To the fives 32. So what are your goals? If you break them out and think about the growth along an exponential trajectory, then maybe you'll get a Series C round.

Yvonne Ivey 35:13

Interesting, because you sort of framed your comment around being offensive. And I don't find it offensive at all. And something that we learned very early on, as we were kind of building this together. Having lots of friends who work in grassroots efforts, I immediately said, Oh, we're doing grassroots efforts. Right now, we're having to think about community building community buy in folks who we probably will never talk to. But there still are key stakeholders. And we turn to a lot of the scientific community building organizations who were who do grassroots efforts, because we're like, we have to not think of this as a like NASA project. But more of how do we actually become entrenched with the community has been doing this work for decades, so that we're not showing up with the meatball and saying, just listen and talk to us. But saying, like, teach us, work with us, become our friends so that we can learn and grow. And I think, you know, as a group, we often say we're building on the shoulders of giants. You know, there are leaders who have been doing this work. And I love that analogy of thinking as a startup, because

Jim Colliander 36:29

this way that I'm embolden, so you can do other things like, you can find a wedge, find the smallest place where you have really strong so called product market fit, whatever that means. And then own that little tiny sector. And maybe that's a very small subset of researchers within AGU. And this one community of ag researchers completely transformed, and you've got the success story. And then maybe in year two, you want to expand the wedge slightly. So there's all of this language and startups and how to build this sort of stuff. But you have to adapt it. And I'll tell you why I mentioned that it was offensive. So after this, like thing that I referenced before, when the transistor was invented, we've had massive investment and global change, resulting from commercialization through venture funding. But the only way it almost seems like the only way to make global change is through market mechanisms with for profit entities. But there are two and probably more striking examples, which are different. The Linux kernel, and Wikipedia, stand out to me as Elinor Ostrom style structures that are different than Facebook, and Google and Amazon. And how to build those is not something that is taught in the accelerator incubator complex across all the universities that are trying to imitate Y Combinator, like a franchise, you know, so if we had a Wikipedia like factory, analogous to all of these incubators, maybe the world would actually be a better place. And the people that are celebrated might be more like Jane Goodall and less like Elon Musk, right. So there is some offense, I have a for profit company, I believe that this is a really important way to change the world. That's not the only way. But the culture seems to reward that as the expected way. But top seems like something else, you're trying to achieve something more like Wikipedia, and less like Facebook.

Monica Granados 38:21

This is Monica, I would just caution though, that like it's a government agency. And so these, there are different constraints. That, you know, you can't just go and work with anybody. And you're kind of also I'm just putting my, you know, my hat on working as a, as a government policy person, that you're at the

whim of the government, right? And then the government of power. I know, we were always worried that like, well, if you know, if a government came in who didn't believe in open science, which is a little bit less likely, because open science sort of process political lines. So, um, you know, in many ways, funding wise, even if you are wildly successful, it doesn't necessarily mean that you're gonna get another, you know, round of investment, just because of the the nature of the fact that you're a government agency. And so one of the thing that it might be worth thinking about is like, what's the succession plan, in the worst case scenario? And so that's something that we do think about in Creative Commons as well, like if we disappeared in five years, because, you know, something terrible happened, you know, what we have a succession plan on like, where are we, where our resources would go, you know, would go to how would that be taken over? Who would who would take that over from us? In like, the worst case scenario? Just just in a way that's unfair, right? Again, you could be wildly successful, but it's, you can't, you can't just have, you know, a philanthropic organization come and take that take it over because we're a government agency, just a little bit more complicated because,

chelle gentemann 39:52

yeah, and we've been I've been thinking about this because I've been talking a lot to like Caitlin and Valerie from the That's an open and we're having a conversation with her and others, to really try and break governance and create this sort of plan so that we are not only for ourselves, but also is, again, a demonstration of how we're trying to work with other groups and learn from the community. Because I do think I do think we made some missteps at the beginning by not having a really clear governance and value system on our GitHub really set out very clearly, this is what we want. We want community, we want to support open science. And we need to play catch up there. So yeah, thank you.

Yvonne Ivey 40:40

And the conversation shows referring to is there's a larger and we didn't include the same Kevin slides earlier. But data and architectures study that's a portion of our team is focused on, and they're looking to better understand how to intersect with our tops initiative. And so we're going to have an open meeting in October, I believe, in October, where we're inviting folks who actually work on how to invest in open science, infrastructure. And so I will share this meeting with the broader group.

Kevin Murphy 41:18

A couple of comments, in response to kind of the earlier ones, I think, I think this group, in particular, kind of acts as a board of directors for tops. Right. So that's what your job is, at least, you know, there are lots of other people here, too, this is an open meeting. But in order to help us kind of focus, and find the areas that are those niches are great fits, right? It, I think this group does two things. One is make sure that, you know, we're not doing this in some sort of government vacuum of, you know, we don't know what we're doing type of situation. And, and to help us really refine a lot of these messages and direct the limited resources, we have to to make it more sustainable over a period of time, or more impactful or whatever. Right. So maybe that first question wasn't exactly right, you know, how do we grow and sustain a community? Like, you know, we could probably revise that question somewhat. It's like, how do we like initialize the community with this limited amount of funding we have, what are the best investments we can make? To do that? Right, there are some things we have to do as a program so that we get, you know, credit from LNB, and all those other people, right, we've got to come up with

these metrics, like 20,000, people are going to be trained and this and that, and this. And those are, those are important to us. Those are things that are driving a lot of the timelines and investment choices that we make. Because typically in the government, you don't even have a KPI like that. Right? They're just like, we're going to start this noble thing, or we're going to start some research. So we were challenged to come up with things that were difficult to do. But, you know, maybe they weren't difficult enough, maybe they were too difficult. That's neither here nor there. But how do we go from where we are now, with your advice, and kind of positioned so we can really see in like, by 2027, some of the more lofty open science goals. The other thing I think we have to be mindful of is when we talk about open science and communities, like, it's incredibly big. Like, it's just too big, right? And we only have so much time, so much funding, so much energy, so on and so forth. So really specifying what those particular things are. The things that you think as, as kind of the advisors to this, this program are critical, right? Because otherwise, it's just a couple of people that are thinking about it. And that's just not the right way to do it. So I would almost throw some of those questions back to you all, and say, Hey, come up and tell us what to do. Because that's, that's kind of the purpose of this meeting, shall if you're gonna throw me out the window, but that's

chelle gentemann 44:16

no, that's what we started the meeting out. We want your advice. We want your help. And we want your comments in a kind way. But tell us what to do. And change, right. Yeah, like we are. We don't have all the answers. We don't we don't are very clear on that. And that's part of also why we are going out to some of these meetings and engaging with the community and like being able to go to CCI and the num focus and like, honestly, it just, we're just learning so much because I think one of the biggest lessons I've had in this last year I was I came into it, as a scientist practicing open science and coming into the existing open science community. There's just such a depth of experience. And a different way of practicing open science and dealing with open source communities is different than the Open Science communities and open governance and just really learning, which is like my favorite thing. So this is all good. I think you raised your hands. Yeah.

Malvika Sharan 45:29

Well, because your Alan Turing Institute, just just to point what Kevin was saying, I think we didn't know, I didn't know what my role is here. Right. Like I'm hearing it. And I, I understand that we're still learning but governance starts here. Tell us what we should do. Right? And if not, then we can just write a letter to NASA, about recommendation that we think that should work for you. If that's because I think what we are really struggling with, and that's okay, because we're still in the early phase is like, we don't know what's happening. What's the, you know, we're coming up with ideas as we're going along, which generally happens in open science. But I think, to do this, you know, growing and sustainability, we'll have to plan way ahead, we'll, we'll need to tell people what we're doing in 2023, where they can get involved, people don't have time, people need to plan ahead. And I think open science needs to do it, because of equality, diversity, inclusion, right, like, because people can plant early on people can, I think it's really difficult for everyone to engage in the same level. So they can decide, you know, Dheeraj, there are multi channels, this is what I like, this is what I can do. Even in this in this group, you know, we all cannot participate in the same level, we all have very different expertise that we bring. So yeah, I mean, we do have some governance experience, if we can build a governance for this team. That could be a template for how we do the governance for SMD work. I think one thing I would say, I'm

so excited by this Biden policy on open access, can we build on that? Can you work with Biden? Because why not? Right? Like they are investing in NASA so much. They want to hear what it looks like, in practical sense, because they said by 2026, you have to open everything, but they don't know what that entails. And you can enable that work in NASA, but also like you can inform the policy at the level where it's needed for expertise that they don't have, actually. So I definitely think NASA should be there. Also creating roles. I think if you finish your first year, and you've identified all these work that people are doing all these champions, give them powerful titles, allow them to make decisions, in some ways, understand what resources they need. Yeah. And, yeah, I think it's really about power dissemination. You know, what, what kind of authorities people have, what what decision they can take, without asking you? Where can they use a logo? Where can they use a slide, you know, just starting from simply there? Because that's the identity building? Can people identify with NASA tops, when they go, they are championing your causes? When they are in a meeting where you're not can they speak about your work, and you need to probably constantly tell them to you to speak about our work, we really value your, your input. I love the startup idea. I think the Open Science incubator idea, which is something we do a lot in open life science, that people bring their project, they build it and you actually go and announce we're so proud that this project has been built in NASA tops, and these people feel, you know, validated for the work that they're doing. So definitely follow up on that structural change. So it's not just about let's build training and skills for people, can we actually make a criteria for hiring as open science or reproducibility? Can we make it a criteria for performance review, which happens we also have in our organization, goal setting every year? Can we add one criteria, make a goal around open science, open access or reproducibility so structural change will take you long and I think that goes really well with monikers Where are you like, you know, get leaving your mark. So you don't need to exist I think the goal should be that you don't need to, you know, five years time maybe it doesn't exist that gap just yeah, we just finished with saying transparency of process making implicit explicit not because it's just open sense. It just allows lightning participation of people.

isabella martinez 49:38

If I may respond to that. Um, so this is Isabella, I'm part of the top tops core team. I want to plus one, the very first thing you said about people need to know what's coming next. In typical research or fashion when I was putting together the like online engagement plan, which I gave you guys all snapshot of I read is a lot about how it's important for members of a community to understand what their role in that can leave. But that is kind of what their role is, is to come get what they need, and then bring it back to where they were before. And that's actually the reason that I already have like the list full of a blog, we're gonna write for the next year together so that people can see the topic that they want to learn about reflected in our plan. So I think that's really important. And I'm glad that you brought it up as well, and kind of validated that as something that we should continue thinking about.

SherAaron Hurt 50:38

I think something that kind of resonated me from what Kevin said, and they'll be, this is sure, Aaron with the carpentry, I guess, what is the impact that we as a panel are going to have? And what are we going to pass on to the next panel? While we have been having this conversation, it just dawned on me, you know, like, this is our last type of in person, and then there's going to be a whole nother team that comes on and gives their input, right. So then what happens there? So if we're giving this information, but then one of the next group says that we don't like none of that, and now it's time to change? You

know what I mean? So he's really trying to think about what is wheat? What is that don't make sense. But what are we as a panel, what is it that we're going to produce? Well, we know we have the reports, but what is it that we're going to say that this is our impact for the incubation phase? And what are we going to pass on to the next team?

chelle gentemann 51:28

And I follow up with a question are gonna say,

Yvonne Ivey 51:32

I'm guessing penny or plus happening with shared a said, regarding the point, it's been so valuable for me to regularly hold, figuratively, post part post mortems to reflect on meta level learnings and recorded as a resource for others and myself.

chelle gentemann 51:51

So we, well, we didn't invent the panel, but we made up the panel for talks. We said it was a one year commitment. And so this actually brings a question that I have for you, is the best organization of the top sort of boards that gives advice organization where it's a 12 month period, and at 12 months, the entire board flips over. Or do we want to start by having some Yeah, no, I know. Exactly. So you can continuity? Continuity. So. So if you can make a recommendation that 50% of the board turn over every you know that maybe we do a six month where we start to ingest some longevity, some new things, people and what that would look like, that would be a really helpful recommendation.

Kevin Murphy 52:43

You know, Kevin, I think that we do need continuity. Yeah, I think one year, especially within a member like this is not long enough. I think it's all based on how much you guys want to participate. So, you know, if you have thoughts on how that should be working, like chelle said, is not a bad idea. I do think you think that, you know, we don't have like a statutory regulation on the number of people in the board. So it could be that, hey, look, maybe we don't want to replace people? Or maybe we did, like, maybe, you know, maybe it just needs to be a little bit bigger to cover these areas, those types of things. I think that those are also valuable. thoughts and comments. The other thing is, and this is kind of the tricky part about government, right, is that we can't really call you like a board of directors, we can call you a review panel. But advisory panel, and you can't be an advisory panel, and you can't give us recommendations. But you can certainly tell us things. And we can then write them down as recommendations. Because NASA thought that or whatever, right? So there are some stupid little things. And there's some very well thought out. And legitimate reasons for those rules, which, which are reasonable, but the way that I look at these types of organizations is give us your advice, your expertise. You're not on here, because we don't You don't know what you're doing. You're on here because you're experts in the field. So number of people, I think, is a good fee of meetings, frequency of meetings, as

chelle gentemann 54:31

next month. Good. Do we want to do three months? Because we are in a very dynamic situation here.

Logan Kilpatrick 54:37

How long should board members beyond or just the members just even getting a sense of like what's happened with the core curriculum development? Just that six month gap has been like, I have no idea. I've been completely out of the loop, if you will, about like how that's evolved. And I think if it was a shorter ending cycle, we'd be able to integrate it and get a better sense of what's happening.

Jim Colliander 55:01

little experience with an organization that formed and then continued. And it was a not for profit organization. So the way that it formed first was through a kind of, again, this was an actual board of directors. But they established what they call it an inaugural board of directors with, I think it was an 18 month timeframe. And the purpose of that board of directors was to be advisory to the founders, the people that were trying to build the thing with the understanding that they were going to wind things down. And one of the main outputs of the inaugural boards effort was to populate a persistent board thereafter. So there was some continuity, some folks on the inaugural board moved into the rest. So that's a mechanism whereby you can, you know, maybe the next year's board can establish this continuity plan, because this might be too much work for us. So that's one is an inaugural board to go manage the emergence of a future board. The second is the reference that we are a board of directors and understand that you can have that language. But that was new to me today. So in an actual board of directors, there are committees that meet more frequently than the board needs. So you might have a committee that's looking at the allocation of funds over time, like a finance committee, maybe it won't have accountability or hold that responsibility, you might have another board that's looking after the training programs, you might have another that's looking after different aspects. So there can be frequency in the committee actions, and then the committee's can report to the larger community. So some delegation and governance within this panel, you might get more cycles out of us, if we're on committees that were really, you know, in our wheelhouse.

chelle gentemann 56:39

Like to do a formal name like NASA Working Group A.

Fernando Perez 56:48

I was just thinking of the exact same thing, because because of two additional reasons. Or one reason and one logistical idea that the reason is that it may be valuable for people in here, and others who may not even be here, but to me add professionally may be able to more easily justify, oh, I can put these many hours into this because I'm actually going to, and if I'm an academic, I will say in my annual sort of community like scientific, external service aspects of my performance review, I am part of the Committee on X or Y or Z as part of the NASA Task Force, even if it's unpaid, right. But But then, by having that explicit structure, people can justify allocating the time in that capacity. And one thing that I can imagine doing logistically is the core NASA people who are kind of paid paid for full time for I would say, for every committee, you have to be one core NASA person who can keep things running, because a committee with one person that keeps some continuity, some works much better than if you allocate the actual existence of the committee and functioning to purely volunteer people. And that balance between backbone kind of backbone people and community service can can work well, if it's engineered the right balance.

Malvika Sharan 58:08

Add to that, Malbec. And I am, I think share might have more to add, because a lot of we're talking about is part of the carpentries executive council constituency. And I feel that some NASA people should have been in the panel as well, just for, you know, continuity perspective that they at least are taking the organizational knowledge and bearing it and they can be long term involved. But also that's like changing the culture from inside, rather than they assuming that these people are coming from outside and telling us what to do without really understanding our research and situation. Yeah, share if you have something to add.

SherAaron Hurt 58:48

Yeah, no, I just the committee piece is very valid. And I think that, again, this is Sheriff Sard carpentries. I like that. This is going to conversation, because as we this is just a one, but as we're in and I'm like, Okay, well. Okay, I said a couple of things in this call, you know, in this meeting, but really, what is the impact that I'm sure Aaron or me the carpenter is left with this and what is you know, what's the torch that is being passed? And the questions that we asked, I don't think that is too much of a feat for us. Be that were part of the integral part of it. I think that even if it's not fully fleshed out, I think that we could have, I don't know, the recommendation, or we could get y'all what we think. However you say that, but we can give our opinions as to, you know, what, what, what the next what the next group would look like. And I definitely love the idea of the continuity of maybe you know, if it's possible, some of us stay on for 18 months or whatever that looks like, but I definitely would like to continue that conversation.

chelle gentemann 59:56

And it could be like, maybe we do monthly virtuals and then six months in person like or, like we have, everything is on the table. And I think that our first lesson from our second meeting was this was too long of a gap. Indeed.

Yvonne Ivey 1:00:14

Like, even as we were going through and, and reading through all of the recommendations y'all provided and may part of it, we were happy that we actually like checked a lot of those boxes and comments where y'all were like you should we suggest you do these things. But I think even in that time, we were like, trying to keep up with what y'all were doing as well. And slack works, but also their slack fatigue. And so we were trying to kind of find a happy medium of like engagement, but also like realizing that y'all have day jobs. And it's not just to advise us. Right. That's your Logan?

Logan Kilpatrick 1:00:58

Yeah, Logan from NUMFOCUS wanted to make another comment going back to what can be done to grow this Open Science Initiative. And I think there's conversation before about what is the thing that, you know, is uniquely NASA that is being brought to the open science community, and one of them was credibility. Another thing that I think that we haven't talked at all, maybe not that much about so far is like the potential exposure that NASA has, and how NASA has potential context to like, get, like an actual media narrative around open science. Like, I don't think that's something that a lot of the institutions and the open source organizations that we're a part of, just don't have as much visibility around them. So it's not possible people are less interested in but I think if people are like, Oh, well, NASA is doing open science. Now, this is something that we should actually pay attention to. And I think that that can be a huge driver for, you know, if there's media contacts, I'm sure NASA has a whole

division of people who do something like that. I think that could be really valuable. And also, another piece that I think Fernando mentioned before, is around a lot of the philanthropic sort of partnerships that are happening. And I think it would be really interesting to think about going back to the conversation of sustainability, is there a world where there's people who are working sort of on this broad open science Topps initiative, who don't actually work at NASA, and they're not being funded by the government, but they're funded or funded by some other initiative that, again, everyone probably agree that this initiative makes sense. And it doesn't need to just be a NASA thing. So I think there's a there can be a cool opportunity there as well. But we just had to find the money. So I'm

Jim Colliander 1:02:36

calling Andrew from to ITC and ubcm changing the direction a little bit away from governance. And whether or not this is a board of directors, that kind of going back to the main question that was posed. So I often hear the phrase the Topps community, or engaging with the open science community. I think that's the that's not the right focus. So we should be instead thinking about existing communities that are working in science, discipline specific communities, and finding ways to transform those communities to become more open. And so I worry that trying to build the Topps community is not the right target. So if we go back to that startup metaphor, if you made a list of say, I don't know, 100 different science communities. And then you tried to assign attributes to those 100 different science communities, some subset of them are going to be working on data intensive stuff, using these data watering holes, others are going to be very different. Some are going to be including and very heavily overlapping with NASA, and some aren't. So if you made a list of all of these big scientific communities, maybe the associated societies, you might be able to find them the three ripest for transformation in year one, or those that are meet these criteria that are most NASA tops aligned. And then the goal is to transform those communities in ways that you want. Now, there may be a layer that intersects all of these disciplines, specific communities that you can start to think of as the Topps community. But I don't think we want a new discipline of science called Open Science. So I would keep your focus on transforming existing science making it more open, rather than creating a new open science community.

Logan Kilpatrick 1:04:25

Tim, I just want to put I think that it makes login from nonprofits. I think it makes a lot of sense what you're saying. I think that there's the flip side of it is there's probably a bunch of value in bringing together a bunch of people and whether or not it's I agree, I don't think the goal should be to create an open science community or a Topps community, but there's probably just having even all of us together, which is sort of a very small micro community. There's been a ton of value, I think, for the ecosystem. So agreed. But I do think that even again, if if there was an open science community that was built with I think there already is one that exists today. And we can sort of build on top of that having those people in the right places is like the organic, grassroots way of disseminating all that information to the communities of pure science that aren't sort of doing it in an open way,

Jim Colliander 1:05:14

can I flip it back to you, I'm thinking of you as the non focus representative. And this kind of echoes on something that Fernando said previously. So open source developers who contribute, say to PI data, some of them are doing so because they have an academic gig. And they're trying to develop the tools

that they need to do their research in a discipline specific area. Others might be associated with a company, and they're doing something that's also open source. But those contributors to the tools that are vital to specific disciplines. I feel like don't have an official role in the pure science disciplines very much. So is there some way here? I'm thinking of you as representing open source developers? Is there some way to bring open source developers into these disciplines, specific communities? Or is there an obstacle there? And we need this like, community of open scientists, broadly. I'm seeing mismatches in making this work. But I'm curious about your reaction to that kind of question.

Logan Kilpatrick 1:06:09

Yeah, I think the reality is, is that a lot of the people who are doing the development of those open source tools, their full time gig, as you said, like is something in a pure scientific domain? I think that's the reality for most people is you like it would be a big lift for you to contribute to open source, if you weren't, in some capacity, like a user of that tool are a bit like I started using Giulia contributed open source while I was doing work at NASA. And I think that's probably the case for Osprey. I don't know if that answers your question. But like the, so

Jim Colliander 1:06:41

the commute the, on my evaluation, at the end of the year, if I made a big contribution in open source, there's not really a clear place for me to claim it to get a raise in the math department. Yeah, but I feel like the discussions here are maybe going to break that down. So the contributions of open source software are going to be relevant in the evaluations of the scientific disciplines. But we're not there yet. And so I'm looking for ways to like maybe my my comment about the tops community is misguided. And instead, we should think of, there needs to be this community of open scientists. But it doesn't feel right. For me, I feel like we need to work within the scientific disciplines and their communities and make those more open. And I feel like open source is a way that we have too little participation in open source tools, little celebration of open source in science. And I feel like this is a mechanism tops where maybe some of that can change. Fernando thinks about this stuff a lot, too. So he brought his sermon for us.

isabella martinez 1:07:40

I was gonna come this from the perspective of it user for a quick second rather than with my top hat. So I don't know if people here are familiar with the movement. Right now. It's create open source software for quantum computers. But that exists. And there's one in particular circ, which is specifically made by Google software developer, so no software developers through that program that Google has, where you spend a percentage of your day working on not your primary project. And one of the big pieces of feedback that like actual quantum computing, researchers had on circ was that it wasn't specific enough to any field to actually help them do what they need. And so it's improved since then. But I'm seeing kind of a similar metaphor to what you were just say, were really, really good software developers develop the language, and then it wasn't applicable enough. And they needed to then create the ability to bridge. So is that kind of like what you were saying, like people who are working on open source software sometimes are coming from the software developer language as background and don't necessarily see themselves as a scientist and therefore not belonging to an open science movement? Or did I miss your point entirely?

Jim Colliander 1:08:58

I think that someone else like this person can answer the question.

Fernando Perez 1:09:03

No actually Isabella that's a great example. And I want to comment on that because I was already thinking in that direction based on the previous conversation on illustrating if you go through a list of the projects that non focus covers, right, which is a little bit of a mini mini universe of like, scientific Python, Giulia and some our ecosystem. Hardly any of those have any were originally created by software engineers. So to give you a very common I was mentioning this to Chelle. I want to make a bit of a personal comment. So the shirt I'm wearing today, was it used to belong to John hunter who here knows who John Hunter was? Only a handful of you and shall it also John Hunter was who knows what network live is? More people so all of you who have used my plan, John Hunter was the creator of matplotlib. He was my Brother, and in 2013, after giving the keynote recite by a week later, he was diagnosed with terminal cancer. And I spent two weeks in the ICU with him and he passed away. And his wife gave me several of his shirts, and I still wear them. And the reason I bought it today was the bigger picture to send to his wife. Because when that helicopter that was out there, flew in Mars, the telemetry image beamed from that control room down, there was a screenshot of a matplotlib when John created matplotlib, because he was a neuroscientist at the University of Chicago, working on pediatric epilepsy for children and wanted to get move away from a first stage highly proprietary, neuroscience specific tool that they used in the lab that required a dongle to like one student at a time could use it. Eventually he was using MATLAB and then we want to get away also from MATLAB, and landed on Python. And because I was trying to graduate and couldn't get take his patch for IPython, he went to create an app of lib. NASA had drain at JPL was one of the first people who contributed to matplotlib back in 2004. Impact of matplotlib has been worldwide. Two weeks ago at the CCI meeting, the current maintainer of matplotlib after John passed. Tom Cassell, who's at Brookhaven showed me the data on analyzing as of right now, every month worth of preprints on the archive matplotlib embeds metadata and everything it makes. So you can actually scan the PDFs, and find out how much of the current content literature uses matplotlib 15% 15% of the current literature that's put out on the on the archive uses matplotlib to make its figures. So John changed the world by giving us a tool like that book led as a neuroscientist working on E coli ElectroCorticography embedded embedded sensors and children's brains with untreatable epilepsy, right, which went to be picked up by NASA. And NASA sent him an email in 2016. And that, if he could get up to speed on fixing the bug on ellipse intersections, really quickly, it wouldn't be great because the probe was on its way to Mars. And they couldn't call it here at JPL. They couldn't correctly get the trajectory intersections plotted. Today, it has changed all the science. But John didn't try to make a library for science, he was solving his own problem, right. And then the last thing Don did before he died, literally the last paper he signed, I think, was the founding papers from our program books, we actually in Chicago, he signed the papers right before he died to create non focus as an organization that now was seeking to change the legal and financial landscape of the open source community. But it began with that specific intent of driving the change he needed. And so you need to identify this is bad, there's a long winded and personal connection to the story of why that notion of these wedges that you can drive very, very deeply through community is necessary, you can take advantage of the leverage of openness to spread widely, right you make the hooks you leave velcro out there for others to attach to but you will drive deeply for impact if you can find those those specific communities in which to have an impact so and I love it answered the question or not but

but to me, that's what resonated and it was something that I kind of had brought also because I knew I was gonna be here. And I wanted to take that picture to send to John's John's widow and his kids. Sorry for the rant sorry, but you may have to follow that that story that's just inspiring. US passionate person calm it actually, it is a happy to have it's a very happy

Malvika Sharan 1:14:18

to talk about community of practice and the comment from Mercury there. But also somewhat the question you asked Isabella, this is Malika. I think the community of practice are for. So we need to recognize not everybody codes. Hi, everybody, software programmer, which is where community of practices very, very important. This we might have definitely brought up with the last panel is that maybe a future direction that this team might need to push for is to invent new positions for research, research infrastructure roles, where people are facilitating these kinds of work across really, really important project, because of course, a researcher has this intention to do the right thing. But they are also debugging code they like in the middle of the night, they don't really have enough bandwidth. So respecting that, you know, they don't have that intention, they just don't have time. So can we hire somebody within those. And this is coming from actually in the team that I lead is a team of community managers in my organization, who sit across different projects, ranging from health to infrastructure to environmental research, and they are in my team, because we want to break those silos. So these community managers talk to each other and talk about these projects and build this interoperability between their projects, building generalizability, right, like, can we apply humanities software in Insight vision, computer vision in landscape analysis, right, and this is happening. So these these roles are very important just to recognize that structure is hard to change pattern, it's hard to change. But there are people who are who love doing this is a bit of a thing. I love doing this, or we were talking with more people here who just love enabling someone else's project. So you know, this is actually in their benefit. And I imagined a lot NASA researcher might want to take those kinds of roles within the organization projects. On the chat, let's see, apo kicked me off the Wi Fi.

isabella martinez 1:16:29

I don't think we have questions. But we've had a lot of really great comments from mercury. Mentioned that after I'd said my thing about the Google software developers that there is a gap in OS expert advice and OS community of practice. And I was just following up to confirm that OS expert advice in this case meant software developers. But I do think that that was the intent. And I will do a call back when we were saying that we are going to GitHub universe, and I forgot the other ones. Reinvent. So we are definitely beginning the reach to that to those areas. But I what I was thinking about when I made my comment, and I think was kind of in the background of this of what you were telling us, Fernando is different groups are going to be motivated by different things. And we definitely need to keep that in mind in our own messaging. We've lost a couple of participants in the last hour, I think people are winding down for the day. Pan, I want to give you a chance to respond to anything, if you'd like.

Pen-Yuan Hsing 1:17:42

Thank you. Well, first of all, I was really inspired by John Hunter's story, I think that really sold me idea sold me on the idea of, you know, finding some sort of niche where a village can be leveraged to really create much broader impact outside of that niche. But my question is, how do we how do we actually

identify where those wedges can be? I am still struggling a little bit on that point. On the other hand, I can really attest to the suggestion of, you know, maybe he breaking down our work into, I think the word was committees or some sort of subgroups, where I can imagine maybe each of us will belong to one or two of those groups. And then each group might have three or four people or something like that. And then we can work with each other to provide more focused. You know, maybe whenever you're seeking advice, which suggestions on how to do that particular thing. I can attest to this, because I found this interesting listening to you describe it, because in the gathering for open source hardware, we were going through a very similar process. This community has existed for a long time. And we wanted to come up with something that does a lot of what a board of directors would do, but we also don't want it to be a board of directors. So technically, it's called the Community Council, but it's doing a lot of the same work. And we were tasked for the first inaugural year, as I guess you can call the inaugural board to come up with a lot of the governance and first of all, we discovered that year really isn't enough for a big community. But second of all, one thing we decided to try is to come up with what we call working groups, or some are working on the community. So those things someone finance some other stuff. And once we started doing that, we discovered that we're making much more rapid progress So, I just want to echo that sentiment that maybe that's a great way to break up the work that we're doing here. And I'll just end by asking, you know whether we can start thinking about that since this is a one year commitment, you know, whether it's the next few action items after our meeting this week, like alright, reconvening in a few months? If so, whether we're going to be talking about working on clutter we're going to be doing in the meantime, that kind of stuff. Like, will there be an opportunity to come up with a more specific plan for the rest of for one year commitment.

Yvonne Ivey 1:20:43

If folks in the room nodding their heads,

chelle gentemann 1:20:46

I think part of the plan, we have sort of like our agenda for today, tomorrow, hopefully tomorrow, maybe we'll have a little bit of time to talk about that. We're going to take a transcript of the whole meeting, and then start engaging with you to create a report within 30 days. And I think part of that report will actually be for you to set out not only the structure of the community panel and how it's going to evolve in time, what our meeting will look like if we want subcommittees, and then also some maybe targets for that. Some goals for the next three to six months. And with that being the initial idea, and I liked the idea of this long term planning for inclusivity. So I think that, you know, start small, and then the next time we meet, we'll start extending those and extending us. And that will also provide some continuity to them. The chair not chair sitting on the line, saying he muted you me, yeah.

Qiusheng Wu 1:22:10

Yeah, sorry, I Eastern time. So I just go home and my kid is watching TV. Those might be very noisy here.

Yvonne Ivey 1:22:25

Nope, problem. We just wanted to give you an opportunity as a panelist to speak.

Qiusheng Wu 1:22:32

So I, earlier I was just listening because I cannot speak. So I kind of have the same question. Data pan just mentioned earlier that all kinds of things that we can do to best contribute to this panel, because I feel that right now we are not contributing. Stop game. So I feel that we are not contributing that much. So I was wondering what kind of external items that we can do after this meeting, because we are not there in person. And so the things we can do is quite limited at the moment and was wondering, is there any plan that we can better work together to contribute to the panel?

Yvonne Ivey 1:23:29

Panels in the room? What are your thoughts? Yeah,

chelle gentemann 1:23:38

so that I'm gonna jump in real quick shifting. So while you were probably having dinner and hanging out with your child, what one thing we did is we had all the panelists go around and say a little bit about what they've been working on and what groups they're involved with, so that we all sort of like shared resources. And maybe you want to talk about your work.

Qiusheng Wu 1:24:04

Yes. So for me, I more like focus on open source, software development and cloud computing. So I've done a couple of packages that have been widely used by the geospatial committees special related to Google ascending and Microsoft, proprietary computer and so luckily, I wanted a proposal that was submitted for developing GMAT and maintaining GMAT was recently funded slated for funding by NASA this the open source framework and library tools data. Stephen was the program director. So we worked over the next two years to best utilize the funding to provide training workshops and improve the GMAT. So that And the geospatial community can better utilize the free cloud computing resources by Google is ending. And we all hoped also to integrate some of the Microsoft planimetry computer functionality into the package as well. And so our goal is to also host some workshops in competencies. And we also have online tutorials, videos for the community. And we also open our Open Access book, they will be available maybe sometime next year, this provide more of a systematic introduction to Google is changing in Python and Jupyter Notebooks. So we try our best to make things more readable, reproducible, and also more accessible, rather than using commercial software and desktop. And, yeah, that's kind of the goal. And I try my best to make also tutorials almost every week, and right now, I think, probably abt, one 100 hours, the YouTube channel that 100 to 200 hours, watch hours, every day, so. So I was thinking that, how can we be better integrate some of those? Because right now, the opening call, the curriculum is more for the general public. But eventually, I think you'd be great to integrate some domain specific curriculum that people can adopt and use in the curriculum, because right now, I think there's no university courses that offer directly this on open science, there might be some very low level 100 level 20 Level undergraduate courses might be half. But when you get into higher level courses, or graduate level courses, then it might be need to be some domain specific so and just echo the comment I made earlier today is that to have a broader impact, I think is we're not going to reach like many people directly. So if we can have some leaders, that we pass the torch to the leaders, and those leaders change the people in their reason, especially, for example, people in the developing countries in Africa, and also in, in South Asia, solos, they have a lot of tea, so they're interested in learning more, but if they can learn from us, and so for example, something like the, like GitHub, the Global Campus, they have some kind of something like they teach so you can sign

up to join a group. And they have some, for example, free sources for them, like Google, or GitHub co pilot, right. And so those people that utilize resources, and then they will introduce them back to the classroom to their students. So eventually, you want to reach a much wider audience, rather than trying to reach to everyone because the capacity is limited. But we need to identify those leaders, for example, maybe you can have a GitHub group or something or whatever channel that you set up, and then recruit people, for example, from local, some leaders in different reason. Because if you're having conferences, not everyone can make to the conference due to time and money issues. So if you have some leaders, and you can learn the materials, and for example, give him some meetings every quarter or every couple months, to see what kind of activities they can lick and promote and they work together. So in that way, you have basically you have seen everywhere you have a torch everywhere, and is lining up. So eventually you will really have a broader impact. Because right now, I think it's still rev De Niro. So if you want to grow the impact, then we need more people to do that. Simply just the the panel itself and also, all you guys doing might not have they go that far. So this was my my two cents. Yeah. Thank you.

isabella martinez 1:29:29

Oh, yeah, the baby. I actually think that the that is a good segue into the next stage of our conversation today, which is our last formal activity before dinner. Sidney if you wouldn't mind returning to the slides, please. So here's the plan. Now I'm going to introduce the GitHub activity before the people who are here in person. Do our break a little different than we did before. so that we can then move into this more like informal, smaller collaboration. And also people who are on East Coast or other non Pacific times, can feel free to log off and collaborate on the GitHub asynchronously. Alright, cool. So if everyone can go to the GitHub for people who have the deck open from earlier today, the link to our GitHub is on the slide that Sydney is displaying now. Next slide, please. As we mentioned, as I mentioned earlier, today, we are in the process of setting up our GitHub, so it's a bit more easy to navigate for a beginner, we'll also take the feedback into consideration that as much as we make GitHub easier to navigate, some people will still find it hard to navigate, but we have to start somewhere. So when you go to our GitHub, you will see that it is generally Oregon. So there are two folders, one, which is called resources, and the other which is called Doc's, do you want me to share?

1:31:45

Yeah, as the next slide.

Cynthia Hall 1:31:47

Oh, it's just so slow right now. Okay, if you go, no worries, if you go into the folder called resources, you will see two other folders called the Open Science cookbook, and the year to open science cookbook.

1:32:01

I wanted my slides,

isabella martinez 1:32:03

it's okay. It's okay. I'll try to remember everything I wrote down. What are these cookbooks, what we are trying to do is create a location where we are pointing to existing resources that we believe will help people who are either just getting started with open science if you are calling to promote our have

learned the basics and want to engage further further engaged, or want to begin a larger movement at the organizations of which they are apart, which we're calling strengthen. So there's the year of open science cookbook, which is specifically about NASA has launched the year of open science. How do you learn more about NASA as leader of open science? How do you engage with NASA zero open science? And how do you bring the year of open science to your own organization? I'd love comments on that. But we're actually going to work on today's the Open Science cookbook. Your Open Science is all great and good. But what about all these other resources we've been talking about today? We also organized it into those three tiers. Strengthen is specifically a curation of resources that I cite, specifically for universities versus government institutions versus private institutions of how they can create open science. Engage is also about understanding what your organization needs. But the promo pages look very sad. Right now, the promo pages are chelle and Isabella got together for an hour and put as many resources that they could think of on a single page and tried to organize them in some way. All of you know your own communities and the organizations that you are both formally representing and informally representing today, much better than I could remember. And like the 30 minutes that I had, so the rest of the time that we will be here in person. And indeed, beyond just these two days, we would really, really love help with the promote open science cookbook pages, because that is what we want to just be our brain dump of all the resources. At this point in time. I don't even think it needs to be that organized. We could go organize it later. But all the things that we've been talking about today, the carpenters, instructor links that we were talking about earlier, aren't on there. The LinkedIn None, none pies, conference, conferences and committees. You get had another name for it, but that you were just talking about are on there right now. So we would love this time to work together to both brainstorm ideas for what even should be on here and also to try to put as many resources as we can offer right now. Crashing has his hand up? Yes.

Qiusheng Wu 1:34:36

Yeah, I was wondering. It may be a good way to turn the GitHub pages into a website or Jupiter boot website because right now, you have lots of content there, but it's all within the directory is not searchable. So if you use a one to something from the resources, you have Right now there's no really it's not a Source Engine. So if you, I can certainly also help, you may want to turn this one into website, automatically abusing Jupiter book. Eventually we have a website and people can search, they can tweak records to the content without having to go through each sub directory. Just a salt. Yeah.

chelle gentemann 1:35:20

Yeah. So we 100% agree. And that is when we bring our project office on in like, soon. That's like their first thing that we're at one of the one of the like 10 million things that we're asking them to do, which is called as content, create a website with a link to a Jupiter book.

Jim Colliander 1:35:43

Yes, yeah. So can I brag on my friend Fernando, I was at that Edie symposium in June, we had the same problem. And then an afternoon of little hacking, he converted a GitHub repo similar to this one into a Jupiter book using a GitHub action. And it was rendered in like an hour and a half. So he's just amazing. So you might want to push his fingers.

Fernando Perez 1:36:03

And when I was actually at NASA, the NASA Edie workshop and by the way to answer anyone's question, what we're referring to is a static generator. It's not Jupiter in the interactive notebooks. So it is exactly a static generator. But I did it in the form of a pull request precisely. So that people basically I added, it's just a couple of lines, literally, like we can do it in five minutes. But I did it in a way that and I'll drop the link into Slack so that it would teach them to pull requests are structured to use it. Basically, I use a small pull request as a way of teaching. How do I take a repo that has random combination of notebooks, markdown files and restructure text files? How do I turn it into a live website, I made that as a sequence of use of very small pull requests for each committed one thing as a way of basically making a tutorial by way of pull request. So I'm happy to

Yvonne Ivey 1:36:56

share the link in a second. Yeah, that would be incredible. And I would be happy

Fernando Perez 1:36:59

to either now or later whenever do it. Like,

Qiusheng Wu 1:37:03

yeah, okay, so because you already have all the markdown, so there'll be a little box up all the markdown in notebooks. So you just add a couple more files, and then have a GitHub excellence, you every time you post the markdown, you can ultimately rebuild the website. So you don't really need to manage the website at all. And like this is going to be much more intuitive for users to locate and resources. And also you can source it can also show up in the Source engine. So people are going to fly you because the gig hub does not the report has no really solid on Source engine on the first page. Yeah.

chelle gentemann 1:37:42

That that would be great. And just to address the earlier question about challenges working in the federal government, I do believe there was about a six week conversation that ended up with us being allowed to have GitHub actions on our website, on our repo. So we are allowed to do this now.

Fernando Perez 1:38:01

I just dropped into Slack the link to that PR, but I'm having to like expand on the topic. And it's just that I figured I want to also to test the idea can a pull request for you teaching mechanism. And so I explicitly like broke down the commences like teaching steps. So

Yvonne Ivey 1:38:16

we participate in the Grace Hopper day, which is the one of the largest hackathons focused on women in STEM. And it was focused around pull requests. And we spent Isabel and I spent the day at the hackathon like with literally us learning how folks that are interactive in this manner. And I was like, I just want to play on GitHub all day. This is great. So yeah,

isabella martinez 1:38:44

we were much less productive with our other work that we were planning on. Okay, so I think chelle Do you want to do your closing statement, and then we'll let the virtual participants let go. And then the rest of us will work collaboratively until four until five? And then we'll be done.

Yvonne Ivey 1:39:02

But we also welcome books online if you if you want to stay along. But

isabella martinez 1:39:06

yes, you are not being you're not being kicked out. I just wanted to be thank you for the time that you've spent here. And what would you allow? Let people leave if they needed to?

chelle gentemann 1:39:17

Yeah. I'm really, really happy we were able to do this in person. I think that yeah. And we were able after lunch with some struggle, but thank you, everyone, and especially Cindy for finding us our upgraded room so that you can hear us so that you can hear us and we're really pen and just saying thank you so much for participating virtually. And so all of you, I mean, we're just gonna have pages of notes and I am really looking forward to the transcript from this meeting all of the comments and the knew that it really makes me so happy that you want to engage more with us. Because that I really feel like we're doing something successful that you want to speak more to us, and that we're really hearing you and valuing your opinion, and that you're feeling that. So thank you all so much for all of your comments. And we will do our best to support you writing this report. And then setting up these continued engagements and these working groups. And tomorrow is focus, like you asked for Logan on the curriculum development, because so much has happened in the development and then the future plans for deployments that Brooks will be talking about. And thank you, Kevin, do you want to say a few words?

Kevin Murphy 1:40:46

One really happy I got to come out here and meet you guys. I think I think the input you provide is valuable. And, you know, I just really asked that, maybe, you know, based on our earlier conversations, I won't be here tomorrow, but that, that maybe you do have some actions for the tops team on on how to, like, really target what they want to get done in 2020 brain. Right? Like, like, give some advice, there may not have to come exactly tomorrow, but but pretty soon. So they can they can plan at where you think we can have the biggest impact. So if there are some, like very specific things like that, that you can recommend, or suggest, I guess, to us, I would really find that useful. Going forward. All right. Of course, you know, we we really like shell just started in this capacity. What? What April, basically, so So you know, we are going pretty quick. All in all, but, you know, we really need to have that guidance on where we can have the biggest impact, because we need to see some sort of progress we need to show. You know, those types of things, especially, you know, we are in the government, like you said earlier, right? Like what happens from year to year, we don't know. So if we can demonstrate progress in tangible ways that have impacts on our communities and constituents. That helps this whole thing last longer. So So when you're thinking about what we do, think about who we need to really influenced to do that, and where we can have those big thing, big, big impacts. And, you know, I like to say I'm in this for the long haul, or as long as they let me be in this privileged position. So, you know, thank you for your participation and guidance.

Fernando Perez 1:43:07

And a question for the Topps team, thinking about what he is saying and thinking about these high impact high high visibility wedges that can help you in that regard. So early as so as Jupiter really began to grow and take off, we got a huge amount of mileage in the community out of a few highly impactful stories. For example, in the LIGO collaboration, published the discovery of the very first paper on gravitational wave detection, right? They actually had Jupyter Notebooks up on GitHub. And what we did was we immediately hopped on, in fact, one of my postdocs beat me to it, I was trying to do the repo, converting it into a binder executable version. And he did it first made a PR and the mileage we got out of going to conferences and showing look, this thing, that is a major physics discovery. But now let a Nobel Prize in Physics, you can click on this little link. And right now on your phone, you can listen to the collision of two black holes. That was huge. The value and it was complete, effectively claiming costs around a half an hour's worth of work, they had done the science. And that was very impactful, very valuable and very important. At one point, we had a demo of how to do an executable paper that was hosted by nature. And that that thing, it actually broke traffic records on nature having that demo. So my question to you guys is, I'm going to guess that, at this point, many of the very high visibility projects that NASA has returned is have elements where there probably aren't like the data is already there are certain things that are already there. So that's not going to be easy, but is there something that you know, you can identify or that we I mean, I don't know your constituents as much can you Try to identify some of those where we could say, Okay, if the following was done in addition, like we've partnered up with nature, and we hosted this thing we did, we set it out back then to prop up didn't exist, the binder didn't exist. But we set that up, we worked on it, and the value was huge. The lego one was even less work to use. And are there things like that I'm giving an example? Because I can't answer it for you, though.

Kevin Murphy 1:45:24

I think that that what, like, we were trying to identify some of those things. Through these kind of success stories is logical. All right. You know, and, and, yeah, they exist. Sometimes they don't, sometimes they're not as apparent, right. Like, there's a lot that goes on. And we get to see only a very small amount of how that works. So, you know, part of it is us knowing part of it is us working with our other groups within NASA, to inform them to know, but honestly, it's a hard thing to do. Right? Like, like, if you see a big release, okay, great. And it has those references, and even better, but if you're trying to see what's going on, on a day to day scientific productivity level, that is, I mean, didn't get not like headquarters only knows enough. And then the senators know more. And then the researchers know all even you know what I mean? It's just like, that chart is pretty high. So I'm just making excuses.

Yvonne Ivey 1:46:28

Well, I wanted to say so when justice 40, which came out of the Biden administration, which mandated every federal agency to have an equity and justice plan, one of the things we learned specifically at NASA is that we weren't meta tagging our proposals that identified all of our environmental justice work. So there was a team that spent four weeks just combing through proposals to identify our environmental justice proposals. And in that process, it was very clear that there's so much going on that unless you're actually acutely aware, you then you don't know. And so as we've been going out and having conversation, I mean, last week, I learned that there's NASA as identified a point of contact to

communicate with tribal communities, and that this person whose sole job is to do that outreach, but also in reach within. And so I think one of the things our team is learning, even when it comes to what are the activities that NASA funds around diversity, equity, and inclusion, and outreach and stem, there's like seven groups who even sit at NASA headquarters, that were all talking around each other. And until I joined this working group, I was sitting there Friday, like five, and I was like, wait, you do what? I do that too. So I think we're in this process, we're having to do a little bit of just talking to learn, and it's part of it is slowing the process of knowledge transfer. But also, we don't really have a bank of lessons learned. So it's, whereas we're going out and having these conversations also learning as well, we did this and it failed. But what happened? Like why did it fail? And so we're trying to do a better job, I think, and one of the things we're building into our organization is sharing our successes and our failures so that we're not having to reinvent the wheel, but also we're not having to fail.

Kevin Murphy 1:48:38

I think I think, you know, you're right. Like if we can find those Pacific nuggets where it wasn't possible without, you know, some tool or some process or enabled by tops like that's what the moon shots are about, right? Then this makes what we're trying to discuss here much easier. And allows it to be brought, you know, like, hey, look, you can actually do it, like, empowers you. Right? So

chelle gentemann 1:49:13

I, one of the things that we're doing is with the project office, we're actually getting content creator and access to professional writers. And we've been collecting some of these stories, like one of the big stars, and I don't know if we'll ever be able to lean in quick enough. It just depends, like the Artemis delay was a, you know, sad thing good for us. But that there's a bunch of actually open science going on with Artemis. And so one of the things that we thought exactly, Fernando, let us try to tell that story while that is in the public's eye. And to continue to in this is sort of more like I think on me right now is we're trying to collect a lot of these and start to write them up. Um, I've not I've been running out of I've been running out of time. Usually I write like Friday night 9pm with a glass of wine. And that just hasn't been happening. And then I haven't been productive.

Marshall Styczinski 1:50:12

I'm running out of time, how important is this good exercise? Can we like push that to a different time? Like, maybe extra time tomorrow and just have this be open discussion, or Yeah, I

isabella martinez 1:50:22

just wanted to introduce, so people knew that please come help me in this area that we were trying to build before January 1, but we don't have to do it,

Marshall Styczinski 1:50:31

because it seems like this is productive.

isabella martinez 1:50:33

Discussion.

chelle gentemann 1:50:34

So one of the things is we started a community call to collect some of these stories. And then we realized that our communication, what we ended up happening was we weren't communicating what we were trying to get. And so we were getting answers that were different than what we wanted. So we're working on that language, then we're going to resend out a call to the community to collect these stories, hold interviews, write them up, because these success stories that Steadicam the some our summer intern who worked with us did have been this hook, like you said, that's why I mean, you know, my story was kind of God, like, I walked into a workshop and I was like, Holy crap, I'm gonna be completely irrelevant in six months, unless I drop everything and learn Python right now. And that was that was that was the fire in my belly? Is that the right there? No, like, get it wrong. I'm just stretching it try.

Fernando Perez 1:51:36

Vertical. That's right. And I think 111 lesson perhaps from some of these things that we did that is worth keeping in mind, which I think is complimentary to the No, I think the moonshots at least, as something where there is a very large and ambitious goal, and they're going to be investment. Some of these things, all we did was like turn, like the last quarter turn of the screw is all we did, right? Most of it had been done. And it was like that extra little bit, it was this one thing, okay, a few days of work with nature, like setting it up, or the like, the lego one was really like a teeny amount of work coming. We think we're just closing that last little bit to them flag up and make it a very easy to share, easy to view, easy to consume piece of information. And there may be low hanging fruit of that nature, which is not to say that the bigger deeper efforts aren't worthwhile. But I'm kind of looking for things that will give you folks, the faster wins with a potentially rather limited amount of new work on your part. So

Kevin Murphy 1:52:41

you can help us identify we're looking for him. Yeah, like if you can help us identify him today's

chelle gentemann 1:52:47

like a new search activity that we can do instead of dancing it tomorrow.

Yvonne Ivey 1:52:52

Give us your ideas on a sticky note.

1:52:55

Logan Kilpatrick 1:52:57

really quick show just wanted to suggest as well, in addition to the open call for actual like stories, it might also be beneficial to think about finding people who can help support you and the team. I'm writing them, and I'm sure there's a bunch of like great open journalism type initiatives that are out there. And those folks might be looking for an amazing story with some great, you know, technical stuff involved.

chelle gentemann 1:53:20

Michael Eisenerz contact information.

isabella martinez 1:53:21

Wait, before I forget, can you add the resources about how to make executables to the Resources page?

Fernando Perez 1:53:40

yeah, I put it on Slack. And? Yeah, yeah, sure.

SherAaron Hurt 1:53:45

Sure. Yeah. Um, I just had a thought just thinking about just hearing stories, like you told the story of the shirt, you tell the story of I just went in and like I realized this happened. I think one of the things that we need to do is really, we're talking about science, but we need to reach the person, right? Testimonials, fine, you know, getting those stories about why I don't really know, besides if we're trying to, you know, increase this number, but so, you know, looking at different ways to, for people to tell their story would be another way for me as I think about when I'm thinking about going into a field of something that I'm unsure, I'm generally going to look for people that look like me, and also looking to see what do people have to say about it to, you know, to get the tangible human effect of it all, whereas we're talking about clients technologies, but we're setting

chelle gentemann 1:54:43

things Jimin and Monica, you guys hit like it was exactly the same.

Monica Granados 1:54:47

Let's quit. I'm just wondering if I wonder if an easy one would just be to ask each person in the panel what our story is. I have a similar story of like, there was a time where I didn't know about open finance and then I went Were workshop and it changed my life. And so I think we all can sort of give our story of like, well, what would like

isabella martinez 1:55:07

to do that tomorrow, we could just do it during lunch, and I can quickly record everybody, then do something with it. That'd be fantastic. Okay, cool, new lunchtime activity.

Kevin Murphy 1:55:18

That's great. We don't even have to look too far.

Jim Colliander 1:55:25

I have two brief remarks. One is the Tonga volcano was an example where it NASA goes, data showed that the Earth rings like a bell. But I don't think we have we capitalized on that. But the open data sharing from NASA enabled and insight into the earth that is somewhat reminiscent of the black hole coalition. It's some waves propagating around a large thing. But I have a different comment, which is really kind of inspired by an ontology that chelle taught me with a twist. So what are the ingredients that produce a scientific result? So it's people compute data, and then it's backed up often by resources. And I think in our paper, we didn't really highlight the resources. But you know, you might need a satellite to do the work, or you might need a particle accelerator. But those ingredients create science.

And so if we think of that, as an ontology that we attach to all of the communities that we might start the way that I described before, you might then try to see which of these communities are most NASA affiliated, they're probably going to be communities that revolve around data that comes out of NASA missions. So now we can filter the list. And then which of these communities are most likely to make the impact from open science in the near term? So I just think that if we think of science as the these advances in the human understanding of nature, those advances are really created by people. And I think the reason we're focusing on openness right now is the digital tools are creating new ways for people to collaborate. So it's really a digital transformation that we're trying to leverage. But digital alone isn't the answer. Because we also have to make sure that we don't just let these people in, and those people are excluded, right. So you have to have governance and community. But focusing on the people aspect of the equation, I think is the top side of thing. And then on the other things that you're working on, it's kind of the compute and the data and other things, but all of them have to be stitched together to achieve the science outputs. I think that language of what is the ingredients that produces science, and you have a few of these ingredient pieces, and then you start to tweak those is a helpful structure, at least for me, and thinking about what tops and more generally open source science initiative can accomplish. That reminds

Malvika Sharan 1:57:46

me of I think we're in a very storytelling mode. The story that I actually teach tell people when I teach them about community building is by Susan Solomon on ozone layer. That's one of the biggest public engagement work ever. Because when people identify that we just have to stop using the hairspray and switch the chemical compound that is less harmful. And they tracked how quickly that moved. And I think the reason she says and it's very, very aligned with what Jim was saying. She says, There are three things are it's now how are you personally affected by it identify that perceptible? How can you assess that? What is the impact? What is the number, so showing the power of data, and practical, where is the practical steps you can take? And then she puts those three bolts together. And there's the center, it says public, what is how to unlock the public power? So So I think it NASA could be also seen through How is public engaging with the work as a result of opening data and software and everything else? How are you going to track that? Because I mean, webinars it takes, of course, that would be one, looking at the number of downloads would be one, but also like going further away and looking at how is it impacting policy, we talked about UNESCO quite a lot. And a lot of recommendations that people are writing, they're actually including NASA dorms in there, right that see there's an organizational change. And there is something that that NASA is thinking about, therefore our country should also think about so I think we've talked about it a lot. It's a you know, federal government funded, we have restrictions. But I think we need to still continue making sense of that when we say open it's open without boundary and without, like National limitation and people from around the world will actually access the data and software that you've published, as well as researchers will interact with each other. So, you know, open science anywhere is Open Sans everywhere. I think there's this XKCD cartoon about this kind of thing. And that's happening which is in Back in the entire world, Matlock matplotlib example is so so powerful. So I feel like, although we are limited by who we can engage with who we can work with, we don't need to lose sight of that people are going to eventually get impacted by it. No, no matter what. But I also want to like, you know, bring back Monica's point that we also need to recognize we can't, we can't engage with everybody, we have limitation, which is where transparency is really important. But yeah, like story storytimes.

Fernando Perez 2:00:33

I dropped a few links trying to help you. NASA said a couple of specific Well, now, they're not really linked, they're just bullet points. But NASA has role in the birth of non pi via and amaray in Paris worth NASA's role in the birth of non focus via Perry as a co founder. I remember Perry giving talks about the calibration software for James Webb being developed at that site like sci fi talks, and talking 10 years ago, easily, right or a long time ago, Perry giving talks about how the calibration software for the James Webb was being developed in Python, open source at the STS, ci, etc. The contributions to matplotlib, early on that, like NASA funding was critical to the birth mean, John started it on his own. But very quickly, NASA made some of first funded contributions to matplotlib came from NASA, both with DSCI. And from Ted rent here at JPL. So NASA actually has some of those stories should be told. And I don't know, they have been told, I don't know. Perry was very active in this world. I haven't talked to him in a while. But but some of that I think, should be capitalized. And in the context of his mission to say, NASA has been doing this, and actually led the way in this space, some 18 years ago. So maybe, maybe you

Kevin Murphy 2:02:01

think like if we didn't capture those activities, right, like, that's pretty powerful for our internal community, especially who we need to convince to change faster. Externally, you know, that, that, that that's also pretty useful. I think, you know, when you were talking about that Nature article, like that just has a big audience, right. Like that's so. So those are going to be fewer and far between? Yeah, I think if we can start to put that corpus of like, what these investments have been, and what the impacts are good day, that would be really a powerful message. And I think that was, that was the point, one of these things, right?

Marshall Styczinski 2:02:44

I have a comment to contribute at some point. I don't know if there's a good time with the stories, or done with those yet. Seems good? Okay, then I'll, I'll launch into it. It's kind of a general comment. But like, I've heard a lot of things today that I wanted to highlight and then cover some of my perspective. So I heard from Malvika, some some parts of of things that you're working on. And then I've also heard from Jim in front and out support for the incentives for especially academics, I see the biggest barrier to adopting open science as the way of science as the castle builders and the the incentive stream for people who are doing science being publishing papers. So there is an inherent built in and deep seated reason to keep your science private. And people get rewarded currently, and have for decades for building their code, keeping it closed off, and not sharing it with anyone. And this is especially bad in the field that I'm in people are like there's a bunch of castles and I'm trying to, you know, put holes in the walls of those castles and BIA you know, everyone can and should collaborate with me. And so one of the the best, like suggestions that I have for trying to facilitate open science and transform to open science and something that I think is really important is is rewarding people who are doing open science. And one way that that happens, of course, it always comes down to money is monetary rewards for recognizing people for contributions to open science. But I also learned about the Badgers last week and and immediately I was like, How do I get one of those? Because another thing that that is a powerful incentive for people trying to do science and who value open science and spend some of their time doing it is things you can load up your CV with that show evidence that you've been involved in projects, and that show your contributions because in if you're for example, Applying to an academic

like faculty position, you need to be able to show what you've been doing with your time to be able to be in the running with other people who may have benefited from, you know, the private castle of being under the wing of somebody who has had one of those castles built for a long time, and has that advantage. So I think the incentives and rewards are really, really important to, to build up people who value open science and participate in it to help convince some of the people at the top of their castle to see that there's value in this and help them see that there's less value in just being off by themselves in their own world. But that's my two cents. And I've heard a lot of great positive things today out of all around the table of efforts that people are working in. And this is a very exciting place for me to be and I'm glad to be here.

Jim Colliander 2:05:56

I want to it kind of reminds me of something that Kevin slide said. So Kevin slides had a slide about values. But when I looked at what you wrote, they didn't seem like values, they seemed like tactics. And value, I think that is building on. What you just said, is what's the value that should be guiding open science. I think it's intellectual generosity. These Castle holders, they're not intellectually generous. They're trying to, like, cobble together their special paths to knowledge at the frontier. But there are really big benefits to being intellectually generous. And it's it's hard to sell that to people, though, that have careers that are built on stinginess,

Marshall Styczinski 2:06:37

they're not always disingenuous as well, I do think that there's a lot of just self serving, this is the best way to advance my career. And it's hard for me to fault people in that position. Although I do often see them as kind of evil. Witches, I think,

Monica Granados 2:06:50

especially like, if you are in like a an underrepresented group, sometimes it is beneficial to keep things to yourself, because you are more likely, you're just in a more vulnerable position. So I think it's just important to have that little asterix, that, you know, we you have to consider sort of like different different lived experiences, from throwing things

2:07:12

out is like, what if I do this, I'll get scooped.

chelle gentemann 2:07:15

We're developing a slide deck. We're developing a site exactly to address this, because one of the things that we

isabella martinez 2:07:23

had when people wanted evidence, why is science broken? Why

chelle gentemann 2:07:29

Why is Open Science better? And what are the fears that I have around open science? And how, what is evidence like actual cited papers? Like what are the what are the fears around being school? What are the fears around? So we're developing a whole slide deck to share with everyone because we get

these questions and these comments so much. And like you said, it's sometimes hard to fault because there are careers, there are labs, there are people who are in your employee at risk, or they perceive it as risk.

Malvika Sharan 2:08:04

So let me turn the

chelle gentemann 2:08:07

question around a little bit, which is, and we've been thinking about this, and we have some ideas, but we haven't really talked about them yet. So I would like to hear your ideas. You know,

2:08:18

we have certain things we

chelle gentemann 2:08:19

can do at NASA, but we're not going to affect tenure and promotion at universities. But maybe we can maybe we can develop a guidebook. You know, I think Fernando and I have talked about this before. Is there something that we could support or do that would help influence the incentive structure that academics are with Amanda?

Fernando Perez 2:08:39

So I have is partly inspired by the first part of Marshalls comments, I was remembering a lesson that we learned. So right now in Jupiter, we just finished restructuring our governance project in a very through a very complicated process. And we were dissolving something that was called the Jupiter steering Council. And long story short, what happened was early on about I'm talking about 20 or t 1314. We formed the notion of the steering council as a way of effectively recognizing the people who have been super active in the project and saying, You've been amazing. You've done so many things for Drupal. Great, why don't you come together and help us like steer it? Now over time, we realized that became completely dysfunctional because it was conflating two things. We were conflating recognition and asking for work on governance. And so it took us a while to disentangle that. But the point is, we learned one thing that we have completely missed, which was for those to whom we said that being named in that position had huge value. And we I have no idea. Of course I saw it as an insider. I began as a grad student like Trump, well getting hired by my advisor, so on and so forth. But to me, that was just like, Thank you for helping me yeah. To those people had the point where Jupiter was became became becoming recognized, being flagged in this way people said, I use that at my job like I put that on. And I was blind to that. So what we did was, as part of dismantling this, we created a different category that we now called the Jupiter distinguished contributor category, which is something where we say, Thank you, you have to you don't have any to anyone. We don't have money. I mean, actually, we do have a teenager to award I think, the most it's a way of seeing things very separate. Do you want to be on a committee? That's a separate story? And now we understand those are different. But there is value in conveying that? I don't know. And I'm sure there's a million legal reasons why NASA can't just hand over your the NASA this. But is there something that can be done, that would flag that, especially for early career people, especially for a postdoc who didn't put out that recognizes this, that you can issue that's a little bit more than a badge, and without getting into the toxic world of like TV awards, and

the number of prizes being given to three people and so on. And so without getting into that extreme, I think you can use the power of this community to recognize and reward people who are doing these things. And that was a big lesson for us. And we,

Logan Kilpatrick 2:11:11

I thought I would show

chelle gentemann 2:11:13

Kevin and I had to stop. I mean, traditionally, within NASA, you recognize contributions by inviting people to be number of science team.

Kevin Murphy 2:11:21

I mean, there, there are a bunch of different. We certainly have like NASA awards, and those types of things that can be given to people outside NASA, they are basically pieces of paper. Okay, but but they're still pretty cool. TV, and you can claim it if you want to, I guess it's fun. Right? So the we definitely have those, we can do that. I think I'm struggling right now, let's see, maybe on the maybe on a top GitHub site, or I don't know how we do it. But, you know, up to this point, we really haven't had something specific for it, that we could, we could, you know, we could support but yeah, that's a great idea. I think we are all so you know, us working with those Institute's or professional societies. And, and somehow, you know, I think, but I don't know what the regulations are shell on, I don't think we can actually fund an award.

2:12:23

So there's no, done yet.

Kevin Murphy 2:12:29

But there are probably ways that that you know, agio everybody to pay for it, every everybody charges overhead when they get a grant. And maybe they can figure out how to do that themselves. Right? If we if we hosted like, so there are lots of kinds of ways people can be creative in how this works.

Fernando Perez 2:12:49

So raised,

Malvika Sharan 2:12:52

money companies

Monica Granados 2:12:53

are returning back to tenure promotion. So if yours is more related.

Malvika Sharan 2:12:58

Yeah, I wanted to say I think that really goes back to you know, give powerful titles to people and build a network of champions. And the example of network of champion that works really well in the UK is software Sustainability Institute, they have every year call, they give everybody 3000 pounds to do the work that they are doing. And these people are either running Code Club, journal club, building

community, and they don't have to do extra work, they just get recognized as fellow and it holds huge value. Because all the people in the network are really fantastic. So giving, getting access so and they publish all their processes, open leads, if you need to adopt it, I'm also happy to put you in touch with people running it. But I definitely think like, you know, those, because I'm a fellow. And I know the impact I've had because I used to work in Germany, I was trying to move to the UK, being in that network really allowed me to look at Oh, there are so many different possibilities that I can go to. So I think there is a real value in that.

chelle gentemann 2:13:59

Thank you. So I'm gonna we have four minutes, Monica telephone fixed tenure and promotion, yeah.

Monica Granados 2:14:04

The four step plan, you probably you can't fix it for, you know, external universities, but you may be able to pull levers within NASA. And that then may be a example that people will look to, to see how you successfully implemented changes in tenure and promotion, or in this promotion within your NASA scientists. That's because you have, you know, the potential connections because you're within the institution to work with your science policy folks who write policy for science. I know that was something I was really excited about when I worked in the government is that you know, I worked on the team that set up the you know, the the promotion the promotion processes for scientists working at Environment and Climate Change Canada. And so if you could successfully implement that at NASA, you could say like, Hey, this is how we did it. And now you know, for promotion not only do you have to publish papers, but you also have We also all have to be open. And you have to contribute. You know, you also get points for countries contributing open data. So, you know, connect with your policy folks, and then use that as sort of like a shining example of how you can transform something that people otherwise see as something that's so static set in stone.

chelle gentemann 2:15:20

Thank you. Thanks so much. shochet, I think last word.

Qiusheng Wu 2:15:25

Yeah. So I can also give my personal example that I just went through, so I just submitted my tiny dossier last month. So definitely. Thank you. Yeah. So for the past three years, I've done a lot of work on open source and open source, open science and open source development. And so I did not publish local papers on the top journals, because even doing open source work, it developed some tools, people can use it. So but the good thing is that so I participate. For example, in open source software, it doesn't have an impact factor is just a drone, other people publishing open source packages, and then write a discussion about it and then publish a journal. So for example, I publish a saw paper about GMAT data query, it goes like, I think, at least 3040 citations within one year, so they may show the impact. And so in my tenure to say, although I don't have a lot of papers in the top journal in the last two to see Yes, but I can showcase that I've done a lot of work in open science and open source. And I have been invited, I think 5060 invited talks at university in different countries, Africa, or some Asian countries and Japan, something like that. And I also have video, they have been watched by several 10s 1000s of hours, and also receive a lot of positive feedback. So that's kind of one component of putting mitosis and I might work as impact. By sorry, I also have some other publication advisors trying

to show that you, you can definitely demonstrate that if you contribute to open side impact, you can certainly see that. And also, because the open source work, I have also received a couple national international awards, they can also show that you're having impact people recognizing you, and also devotees, the NASA community panel is also one of those right? If I'm not doing that kind of work, I will not be noticed and will not have the opportunity. So this also as important, the opportunity and also, potentially, for example, NASA funding, if you're working on the area, you might some one day, you might also get some NASA funding. So though all can contribute to the tenure dossier. So not just like looking at papers and citations, I think it's more like the broader impact how many people have reached, and how much work have you put out there they have been utilized, or even be used by other universities for teaching. And also people will reach out to me or even students that I never know, reached out to me thanking me for providing those tutorials. So in my thanks to those, I think I put up like 20 pages of us. Thank you comments from people around the world and also on social media, they can showcase that my work is valuable. And there's no such thing counting papers and quants. Yeah. Would you be

isabella martinez 2:18:25

interested in writing a blog about making your 10 year case about?

Qiusheng Wu 2:18:33

Yeah, but yeah, so right now is under review. So I will not wait no result until Yeah, I'm happy to share the

2:18:45

excuses for the committee.

isabella martinez 2:18:49

But yes, if anyone has, like powerful stories like that, I think we've been talking about the value of a story that gets you excited or gets you invested. But also, teaching stories are also great. So if you ever don't want to write something, but have a great idea for a blog, just like jump on a web call with me in Sydney, we will record the conversation, we'll write the blog for you. And then you could just, you know, sign off that we captured your thoughts directly because we want like, we want everybody to know like, examples of people who look like you people who have more similar stories to you like, even if you can go and like find there are some great like, papers that have been written lately about how to get started with open science. But there's also something very powerful I think about having a face and having like, people's, like, told more naturally and less papery.

Qiusheng Wu 2:19:43

Yeah. One last thing I like to add is also because the some of the open source work that I've been doing, so I was invited to join the Google Developer expert for Google ascending. I also a note recently invited by Amazon to join the visiting academic program, although I've went through the interview, but I was offered the position last month. So if I officially, I'll be joining Amazon in two weeks a part time jobs part time, working eight hours a week for them, but you also work in open source geospatial projects at scale. So Amazon has the infrastructure, they allow me and the team to work on large scale projects. So they've been I've seen, potentially my also collaborate with tops to see how we can bring some of

the training whatever they can provide to people at a global scale. And so I think there's another benefit of doing open source AI. Without it, I will not be noticed by Amazon and to have the opportunity to work with them in the next two to three years. So this is also very exciting for me personally. So I think it's a lot more beneficial than publishing a paper, you know, top journal, people can read a site, but you don't really have that kind of personal connection to people and also being notified by big tech that potentially can offer some opportunity for you and also for students also for the university. So I can talk to universities, and this is good for me professionally, but also good for students, because Because Amazon can provide organic internship opportunities. So if you have any students, they have the project, and then they can easily be introduced to work at Amazon and eventually hire so I think it's a beautiful mutual benefits to to everyone so they may open source. Open Science is very important. And I am going to continue to vote on that and also try to advocate in in the Amazon visiting academic position.

isabella martinez 2:21:59

Thank you, thank you. And

Yvonne Ivey 2:22:05

with that, thank you, thank you, thank you, thank you so much for dialing in, logging on, flying in for day one of our tops panel. At tomorrow we will have further discussion about tops activities, as well as what AGU and our subject matter experts have been working on in our community develop curriculum.